

Borders Shaping
Perceptions of European Societies

Deliverable 5.1: Story Maps

Project acronym	B-SHAPES
Project name	Borders shaping perceptions of European societies
Grant agreement no	101095186
Work Package	WP5
Document name	Border landscapes as heritage – Theoretical and practical guidelines for reading the Story Maps
Lead Partner	University of Oulu

Document information

Work package no	WP5
Responsible Task Leader	Eeva-Kaisa Prokkola (UOULU)
Authors	Eeva-Kaisa Prokkola (UOULU), Fredriika Jakola (UOULU), Dorte Jagetic Andersen (SDU), Sara Svensson (HH), Tomas Nilson (HH), Oriana Miraka (HH), Petranka Nedelcheva (HISTORYMUS), Dimitar Karaneshev (HISTORYMUS), Mette Fentz Haastrup (SDU)
Other contributors	Magdalena Marinova (HISTORYMUS), Thomas Kaarsted (SDU), Anne Kathrine Overgaard (SDU)
Project coordinator	Martin Klatt (SDU)
Sensitivity	Public
Deliverable type	Report
Date of submission	March 2025

Content

Executive summary.....	3
Links to the digital StoryMaps.....	5
Introduction	6
Aims and objectives	6
Methodological premises	7
Theoretical and contextual insights into border landscapes as heritage	10
Border landscapes as heritage – a way forward	10
Border landscapes and institutionalized heritage	10
Finnish-Swedish border	11
Danish-Swedish border.....	12
Danish-German border	12
Bulgaria-Greek border.....	13
Border landscape as people’s heritage	14
Research process, material and methods	16
Borderwalk as a method	16
Production of StoryMaps	20
Ethical considerations.....	21
StoryMaps of the border regions	23
Finnish-Swedish border region	23
Short description of the area	23
Implementation of the borderwalks and the StoryMap	24
Danish-German border region.....	29
Short description of the area	29
Implementation of borderwalks and the StoryMap	29
Swedish-Danish border region	34
Short description of the area	34
Implementation of the borderwalks and the StoryMap	35
Bulgarian-Greek border region	39
Short description of the area	39
Implementation of the borderwalks and the StoryMap	40
Results.....	43
People’s relations to landscapes: narratives and affects including dimensions of past, present and future	43
Different age groups perceptions of borders’ impact on landscapes.....	49
Common nature and landscape bring people together across borders	53
Discussion	58
References	61

Executive summary

In this report, we present the conceptual and methodological premises for researching border landscapes as heritage and for producing the digitalized StoryMaps. A narrative approach together with citizen science have guided the research process and methodological choices. This has allowed designing research activities and analysis through which knowledge and understanding of border landscapes as institutionalized heritage and people's lived heritage has been gained. Following the principles of citizen science, borderland citizens have been engaged in several phases of research.

We have conducted research and citizen engagement in four European border regions: Tornio Valley (Finland-Sweden), Schleswig (Denmark-Germany), Öresund (Denmark-Sweden), and the Bulgaria-Greek borderlands. These European border regions are fruitful locations for examining the entanglements of borders, landscape and heritage, and how borders shape the perceptions of European societies. The border regions form specific geographical and historical research contexts. The Öresund forms an urban border landscape with a maritime border. The other case border regions share land and water borders and are characterized by rural and urbanized landscapes.

The research involved several stages. First, we conducted desk research to investigate the institutionalized heritage narratives of the border landscapes in each case border region. The identified narratives offer a background for contextualizing the border regions in this report and for the StoryMap. Second, to gain understanding of border landscapes as people's heritage, we developed a research method and technique called borderwalk. The borderwalk is a mobile interview method that is especially beneficial for studying people's perceptions of border landscapes and for exploring place-based narratives. In total 42 borderwalk focus groups were conducted with young and senior citizens in the four border regions, engaging 174 borderland citizens. The borderwalk group discussions were tape-recorded, transcribed and geotagged. Third, we examined and processed the research material to create the StoryMap manuscripts of the border regions. This was done by employing three different and complementary techniques: researcher's selection of stories, participant consultation, and StoryMap workshops where citizens were engaged with the interpretation and selection of the materials by creating posters. Fourth, we edited and digitalized the StoryMap manuscripts with the help of ArcGIS Online StoryMap program.

The key outcome of the research, the digital StoryMap, brings together the institutionalized heritage narratives and people's spatial, place-based narratives of border landscapes as heritage. The StoryMap introduces the cultural and nature sites that local borderlanders value and consider meaningful and provides understanding of how borders shape young and senior citizens' perceptions of landscapes as heritage. The results point out that many sites presented in the StoryMaps are important for young and senior citizens, on both sides of the borders. The narratives that the young and senior citizens told in and about the sites visited as well as the wider spatial narratives also differed from each other. Youth highlight a familiar relationship with the border landscape and their stories more often relate to the practices of border crossing rather than cultural connectors. The senior group narratives were often tied to shared meeting places and past social gatherings. In these narratives, the border was portrayed as a place that has shaped who they are and what values they have. Living with a border landscape was often articulated as having a unique sense of place and identity that is different from the rest of the country. The StoryMaps also illustrate that shared nature and especially border waters are important for many borderlanders. Border waters form simultaneously a bordering and bridging landscape element. The senior citizens specifically perceived and narrated the border landscape in terms of local and national heritage. Although maintaining free movement across the border was

seen as of high importance in the northern European border regions, the role of the European integration perspective was largely absent from the discussions.

The research offers new knowledge and insights into local perceptions and narratives of border landscapes. The stories presented in the StoryMaps point out that for many borderlanders the institutionalized border heritage is important, and they make sense of their everyday environments and personal experiences of borders in relation to wider, public border narratives. Many border landscape narratives celebrate a rich shared history and vibrant cross-border culture. The narratives do not always acknowledge the diversity of voices that shape the border landscape today. Also, some important environmental questions are completely absent from the narratives of border landscape as heritage. The results highlight the importance of facilitating the inclusiveness of border narratives and heritage-making at local, national and European scales.

This StoryMap report and the digitalized StoryMaps are based on research conducted by WP5 partners; University of Oulu (UOULU), University of Southern Denmark (SDU), Halmstad University (HH), and the National History Museum of Bulgaria (HISTORYMUS) with contributions from other B-SHAPES consortium members. The division of work and responsibilities have been distributed in the following manner: Prokkola is responsible for writing the introduction and the conceptual and theoretical framework of border landscapes as heritage research as well as the research ethics section with contribution from others. Jakola, Prokkola and Andersen are responsible for writing the section on research design, material and methods with contribution from others. Jakola is responsible for writing the Story Map production section, for the digitalization of the StoryMaps for the project as well as instructing the B-SHAPES researchers about the StoryMap manuscripts. Each partner organization is responsible for data collection and management, the production of the StoryMap manuscripts as well as reporting the key findings in regard to their case border region. Jakola and Prokkola (UOULU) are responsible for the data collection in the Finnish Swedish border region. Jakola is responsible for processing and analyzing the data and for the StoryMap manuscript with the contribution from Prokkola. Andersen (SDU) is responsible for the data collection and research in the Danish-German border region, for the processing and analysis of the material and for the design of the StoryMaps manuscript. Nilson, Miraka and Svensson (HH) are responsible for the data collection and research in the Swedish-Danish border region, the processing and analysis of the material and for designing the StoryMap manuscript. Nedelcheva, Karaneshev and Marinova (HISTORYMUS) are responsible for the data collection and research at the Bulgarian-Greek border area and for processing and analyzing the material as well as for the design of the StoryMap manuscript. Fentz Haastrup (SDU), with contribution from Kaarsted and Overgaard from the SDU Citizen Science Knowledge Center and Prokkola, is responsible for writing the section about citizen science for the Introduction. All team members have contributed to writing the results section regarding their own region specifically and to providing feedback for others. The discussion section has been composed and edited by Prokkola and Jakola with a major contribution from others. Klatt and Opiłowska have provided valuable feedback and minor editing for the report. The research and StoryMaps have been co-created with the border citizens of the four case regions, and we are grateful for their contribution and their valuable time and support for this research.

Links to the digital StoryMaps

Finnish-Swedish border region:

<https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/f9b3787d6eea44a99946bfbe3b8c2fc9>

Danish-German border region:

<https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/640f945686684680a649804916ceff6c>

Swedish-Danish border region:

<https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/b3c8e71ed87e40eeb6a25a0e75b56a62>

Bulgarian-Greek border region:

<https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/22d61a08fd2149ab932b6949061b9b7d>

Introduction

Aims and objectives

B-SHAPES research on border landscapes as heritage investigates people's perceptions and narratives of natural and cultural heritage in a local transboundary context and in what ways they relate to institutionalized border heritage, such as cultural and nature heritage recognized through nomination and made visible at national, regional and local heritage catalogues, museums, exhibitions, events and others. In the European Landscape Convention (2000) landscape is defined as "an area, as perceived by people, whose character is the result of the action and interaction of natural and/or human factors". Landscape is also understood to contribute especially to the formation of local cultures, heritage and identity as well as human well-being more broadly. B-SHAPES aims at generating new understanding of border landscapes as areas that are perceived by people as institutionalized heritage and people's heritage by combining different theoretical perspectives on landscape. We have gained inspiration from traditional visual and textual landscape studies which discuss how different ideologies and power are inscribed in landscapes and their textual and visual presentations (Häyrynen 2000; Raivo 2002; see also Duncan & Duncan 1988; Duncan 1995). This approach helps to navigate the institutional heritage of borders and border landscapes communicated and authorized through nomination and public commemorations. Second, to gain understanding of how local people perceive and value border landscapes as heritage the definition of landscape is broadened to include material and lived-in phenomenon, people's lived experiences and narratives of landscapes (see Tolia-Kelly 2011; Wylie 2009; 2013), thus responding to the call for "peopling" landscape and heritage narratives (Harvey & Waterton 2015: 906).

This research report introduces the conceptual and methodological premises for researching border landscapes as heritage and for producing digitalized StoryMaps. It responds especially to three objectives of the B-SHAPES research:

O5.1: Studying people's relations to landscapes: narratives and affects including dimensions of past, present, and future.

O5.2: Study how different age groups (youth, elderly¹) relate to borders' impact on landscapes.

O5.3: Provide new knowledge and understanding of how common heritage of nature and landscape can bring people together across borders.

To reach these objectives, we conducted research in four case borderlands: Tornio Valley (Finland-Sweden), Schleswig (Denmark-Germany), Öresund (Denmark-Sweden), and the Bulgaria-Greek borderlands. These European border regions are fruitful locations and "laboratories" for examining European societies (Knippenberg 2004) and entanglements and connections between landscapes and heritage-making. In the border areas people live near each other, attach with and nourish the same natural and cultural elements, yet at the same time their identity and place narratives may differ considerably. The research conducted in the four borderlands together with the digitalized Story Maps provides the starting point and resource for responding to the two other objectives of Border landscape as heritage research that will be addressed also in the forthcoming workshops and dissemination activities of the B-SHAPES project which aim to bring together different stakeholders and authorities to discuss and plan inclusive borderland heritage for the future (O5.4)

¹ In the report and digitalized StoryMaps, we use "senior" term instead of "elderly". The elderly term can be found as offensive by participants (61+) who are, for instance, still in working life as in some languages the translation of "elderly" refers to people with lowered functional capabilities.

as well as assess the possibilities for the heritage industry to contribute to transborder landscape heritage and conservation (O5.5).

The border landscapes as heritage research contributes to border studies and human geography literature by establishing a new dialogue between a place-based approach and the identity-based theorization of borders, directing attention not merely to identity politics but also towards shared land and waters (Ochoa Espejo 2020), the biosphere and ecosystems overrun by and straddling across political borders. The research results offer new knowledge and understanding about local perceptions and narratives of important sites and elements of border landscapes and their temporal and spatial dimensions. The research contributes to border studies and heritage studies by bringing together institutionalized border heritage together with people's perceptions and narratives of borders, two mutually constitutive and intertwined sites of making and sensing landscapes as heritage which, however, are often approached as distinct spheres of heritage.

B-SHAPES Border landscapes as heritage research contributes to societies by facilitating a more inclusive understanding and development of heritage. B-SHAPES aims towards more inclusive landscape and heritage policies underlined in the European Landscape Convention and heritage policies. It focuses on natural and cultural elements of border landscapes and sheds light on meaningful places and elements of landscape that may not be officially recognized but are important for the borderlands and border citizens. In this research, borders are understood to materialize beyond the actual physical border lines and zones; through societal discourses and practices of bordering (Newman & Paasi 1998) and through landscape as palimpsest, as “an amalgamation of piecemeal remnants or traces of past and present processes and their resultant form” (Simm *et al.* 2024: 90). Historical traces and relict borders as layers of landscape palimpsest may have a strong effect on the mental maps of local people (see Kaisto 2024) and in the institutionalized heritage of a border region (see Raivo 2002). By following this understanding, borders landscapes as heritage are not merely present and meaningful in areas and places of immediate proximity to state borders but can be observed and studied in places and sites that carry the traces of national and imperial border constructions, taking the shape of a relict or a phantom border today (Więckowski 2022; Kolosov 2020).

The research of border landscapes as heritage offers knowledge of possible conflicting and bridging elements of borders from the perspective of institutionalized heritage and people's heritage. Mutual understanding of the value of transboundary landscapes and the strengthening of the bringing elements is crucial for preserving the unique landscape qualities and facilitating common landscape management strategies. B-SHAPES Border landscapes as heritage research offers knowledge of possible conflicts of interest in borderlands and facilitates an understanding of borders as a bridge and a resource (Sohn 2014; Prokkola 2008) by highlighting the preservation of the natural and cultural sites in the border landscape that are valued by local borderlanders, opening new pathways for re-envisioning the role of borders in contemporary Europe.

Methodological premises

Narrative approach together with citizen science have guided Border landscapes as heritage research process and design. The combination of a citizen science approach and narrative methodology allowed designing research activities and analysis to gain knowledge and understanding of institutionalized heritage and people's lived heritage.

The narrative approach (Prokkola 2014; Czarniawska 2010; Esin *et al.* 2013; Squire 2013) offers a sophisticated theoretical and methodological starting point for exploring how borders and border landscapes are framed and interpreted as institutionalized heritage and as people's heritage. Following the B-SHAPES border narrative typology – public narratives, spatial narratives, personal narratives – (also Dolińska *et al.* 2021), all

border landscape narratives identified and discussed in the report can be understood as spatial narratives attuned to communicate socially shared, public and more personal meanings of borders, borderlands and places. Both public and more personal border narratives can be put into work to communicate the meaning and values assigned with borders (Prokkola 2008). The latter, personal narratives, refers to stories told by individuals about their own experiences and perceptions whereas the former, public narratives, refers to more widely shared narratives and can be found from various publicly available texts and documents. These are not inseparable and need to be understood in terms of discursive meaning making (see e.g., Taylor & Littleton 2006; Prokkola 2008), for example individual stories of borders often communicate personal interpretations of the past and they can be simultaneously entangled with actual historical events. Some narratives may also be known locally, as local border narratives or border folklore. Such narratives may not have been documented in a written form but are familiar and meaningful for local people and shape their perceptions of borders (see Laurén 2012). Such border landscape narratives told by borderlanders can be understood as inherently embodied, as human bodies have the capacity to traverse, recognize, narrate and 'be' within the landscape (see Tolia-Kelly 2008: 118). Hence, rather than focusing merely on textual end-products, as is often the case in narrative research, our research laid emphasis on embodied narrative activity in distinctive 'narrative environments' (Gumbrium & Holstein 2009), the borderlands. Public and personal border narratives, making sense and communicating the meaning of borders and "border realities" are important for understanding, experiencing and conceptualizing border landscapes as institutionalized and people's heritage.

The citizen science approach underlines and leverages the active involvement of citizens to advance both scientific discovery and societal engagement. For this research, the citizen science approach has been especially fruitful for designing research activities for studying border landscapes as people's heritage and for co-creating the material for digitalized Story Maps. The designing and implementing of citizen science activities in B-SHAPES are inspired by the model of three fundamental elements of citizen science developed by Golubic and others (2017). The first element, inclusion emphasizes engaging citizens in research activities, whether through data collection, observation, or other forms of active involvement. The second, contribution, highlights the mutual benefits extending to both science and society. Researchers gain access to valuable data and broader perspectives, while citizens develop scientific literacy, acquire new skills, and become empowered to address societal challenges. The third element, reciprocity, underscores the importance of two-way communication between researchers and society. This involves more than simply collecting data from citizens; it requires providing feedback on how the data is utilized, sharing research outcomes, acknowledging citizens' contributions, and fostering ongoing dialogue throughout the project's lifecycle (Golubic *et al.* 2017: 2–3). The models on the levels of participation (see Kloppenburg 2022; Shirk *et al.* 2012), however, illustrate that the degree of involvement can vary significantly. For example, contributory projects involve citizens primarily in data collection, while collaborative initiatives engage citizens throughout the entire research process, from defining research questions to disseminating findings (Kloppenburger 2022; Shirk *et al.* 2012). Kloppenburg's model was utilized in the planning of B-SHAPES research activities and to ensure that "borderland citizen" are engaged in several stages of the researching border landscapes as people heritage.

Border landscape as heritage research included four intertwined phases and tasks where citizen science and narrative methodology offered methodological guidelines. First, we conducted desk research on the institutionalized narratives of the border landscapes. The investigation was focused on academic research on the border regions and their landscapes as well as on other textual material (local history books, reports and documents, internet homepages) with a focus on the border regions. Second, to gain understanding of border landscapes as people's heritage the research teams members conducted "borderwalks" in the case study borderlands together with local people, the "borderland citizens", to learn about places and sites that are

important for them and their perceptions, experiences and stories of the border and the border landscape. The borderwalks were documented with the help of photography and by tape-recording spatial, place-based narratives with specific geographic location information. Walking the border landscape and visiting important sites together with citizens offers understanding on those aspects of border landscapes which are mediated by people's spatial perceptions, attitudes and emotions. Third, the research teams organized and examined the material that was collected during the borderwalks and selected "little stories" that best described the sites visited and people's perceptions of the border landscape as heritage. Our participants, the borderland citizens, engaged also in this research phase by offering feedback as well as by participating in StoryMap workshops where they worked in small groups to discuss the sets of research materials and to create posters based on the materials. The borderland citizens have therefore contributed to the research on border landscapes as heritage with their insights on the topic by participating in the data collection and interpretation of data. The stories and photographs of places and sites that were selected and introduced by our participants, the border citizens, have been digitalized by using ArcGIS Story Maps. The Story Maps are open access ([ArcGIS StoryMaps](#)) and will form the material for the forthcoming B-SHAPES workshops with regional and local authorities and citizens. This allows us to gain feedback and reflect on the research and its outcomes together with the authorities and borderland citizens, thus adding a new element to and strengthening our citizen science approach.

The next sections will offer theoretical and contextual insight into border landscapes as heritage, the research material and methods as well as the production of digitalized StoryMaps of the four border regions. The research results offer understanding about people's relations to landscapes and what narratives and affects, including dimensions of past, present and future shape people's understanding of borders in different European border regions with a specific focus on how the perspectives and narratives of youth and seniors relate to borders' impact on landscapes. The results offer knowledge and understanding of how perception of landscape as common heritage can bring people together across borders.

Theoretical and contextual insights into border landscapes as heritage

Border landscapes as heritage – a way forward

Scholars have studied public perceptions and narratives of border landscapes in different contexts and from different perspectives. The role of border landscapes in the national imagination and iconography has been examined abundantly (e.g., Raivo 2004; Häyrynen 2004). In state-of-the-art border studies literature, such nation-centric reading of border landscapes has been accompanied and replaced by transboundary imaginations of borderland spaces, manifested by the shift from thinking through to borderlands towards borderscapes (see e.g., dell’Agnese & Amilhat Szary 2015; Kaisto 2024). Similarly, in heritage studies the focus is shifting from bounded perceptions of heritage towards border-straddling heritage (Harvey & Moustaffi, forthcoming) and towards recognizing how heritage-making in itself often contributes to bordering dynamics (Andersen & Prokkola 2021). The connection between borders and heritage has been contemplated in the field of tourism studies, too. Timothy and Więckowski (2022) have examined the ways in which borders are produced for touristic purposes, commercializing them as cultural heritage and excitement. According to them, borders can be viewed as heritage in terms of national exceptionalism, dark tourism, neighboring relationships, local heritage narratives, infrastructural landscape, and cross-border cultural resource (Timothy & Więckowski 2022). Scholars have also investigated how the history of border and border cultures is produced as multiscalar heritage in the context of museums and touristic events, including the heritageization of European border landscapes (Prokkola & Lois 2016; Dzikowska et al. 2023). Landscape research is highly multidisciplinary and therefore relevant research on transboundary landscapes can be found also from ecology and nature conservation literatures (e.g., Liu *et al.* 2020), also with a focus on the European landscape convention (Gazzola *et al.* 2019; Konkoly-Gyuró *et al.* 2018).

The research shows that although border landscapes are typically associated with national heritage and iconography, European integration and the strengthening of cross-border cooperation partly challenged the national landscape discourse. The Europeanization of border landscapes manifested through infrastructural and discursive changes, adding new symbols and layers of meaning to the local landscape (Prokkola 2010). More widely, the European heritage narrative has focused on the pacification of border regions, making them play the symbolic role of sites of reconciliation for the traumatic experiences of past wars (McCall 2014; Andersen & Prokkola 2021). In recent years, however, the transition towards shared border landscapes has been challenged by the rise of protectionism as well as the introduction of border interventions and fences as a state-centric response to the fear of voluminous migration and the COVID-19 pandemic. The next sections offer insight into the institutionalized, public narratives of border landscapes and for understanding border landscapes are people’s heritage in the post-pandemic context.

Border landscapes and institutionalized heritage

Border regions and landscapes do not have natural-born meaning but people and communities narrativize and assign value to them in relation to their life projects (Entrikin 1991). Hence, our examination of border landscape narratives has departed from an understanding that there is not just one narrative of a border region and its landscape, but parallel and overlapping political and cultural public narratives. The production and maintenance of border-regional landscape narratives often take place through education, literature, tourism and media discourses among others as well as through local folklore and personal life stories. Such public landscape narratives can point to the varying elements about nature, history, economy, culture,

language and other elements that are seen to characterize the landscape, and which help people and groups of people to explain how a regional landscape can be distinguished from other places and landscapes (see Paasi 2003). The analysis of public narratives and discursive production of border landscapes as heritage needs to consider also the contextual and institutional sites of their production (see Fairclough 1992; 2003).

Our investigation has focused on different sites and contexts where public narratives of border landscapes are reproduced and discussed. First, we conducted a state-of-the-art investigation of how the border regions and their landscapes are discursively produced and narrativized in history books and research articles. Second, we examined national and regional planning and heritage documents, place-based educational material used at the local schools, and the regional tourism material. The tourism material was mainly collected from the region's tourism destinations (Internet homepages and brochures of tourism destinations in the border regions). The educational material and information about the material that is in educational use was achieved directly from the local schools, but some were also available from the Internet. All WP5 research teams followed the coding schemes that were designed for operationalizing the WP5 border landscape data collection framework into worksheets. The key findings of the desk research were compiled in a document that was disseminated among the consortium members (WP5 Internal report 2023). In addition, the tourism material has been utilized in a scientific article (Prokkola *et al.* 2024).

The desk research shows that national and local-national views dominate the public narrative of border landscapes, but we found also other overlapping versions of border landscapes as cross-border heritage. The national landscape narratives often underline cultural differences and differentiation of the landscapes whereas local cross-border narratives relate to cross-border cooperation and its symbols in the landscapes. An important yet often overlooked element of borderlands are waters that both connect and form a border, thus forming an open landscape that can be filled with many different meanings and stories from the past, present and future. Other different key themes of border landscape narratives are border and migration control that have occurred in history and have been reinvented in the last decade. Based on the desk research, we found that different 'border narrative' themes can be identified from research literature and public documents discussing the border landscapes and their historical formation in all case border regions.

Finnish-Swedish border

Swedish-Finnish border landscape is often narrated through the theme of a cultural borderland. The history and time before the border were drawn together with the traits of multicultural lives in the shared landscape are important elements of public narratives (Elenius 2008; Nordberg & Kallio-Seppänen 2010). Many narratives take the year 1809 when the border was established in the Peace of Fredriksham as a point of departure. This narrative especially highlights how nature and water play a role as a scene of border drawing. The border, drawn as the deepest and most streaming part of a river, divided the harmonious nature and cultural landscape (Elenius 2008; Pekola 2021; Ruotsala 2021). The narrative underlines that before the border was drawn the parishes and the lands belonging to local farmers were located on both sides of the river, which served as a means of communication between villages. The border caused many landscape changes and rearrangements in land use and in the built environment of the river valley (Hederyd 1992). The narrative of divided border landscape is accompanied by narratives of cross-border cooperation which connects the border landscape together with Nordic and European institutions. The transformation of the Finnish–Swedish border landscape has been narrated against the process of European integration and geopolitical change (Prokkola 2010; Jakola 2016). The history and rights of a regional linguistic minority, Meänkieliset, has become an important part of the regional institutionalized narratives and has been utilized in local and regional heritage-making and production of cultural events (Ridanpää 2011).

Danish-Swedish border

The Danish-Swedish border landscape around the Öresund strait has gained significant academic and policy attention. This is especially with regards to cross-border cooperation and joint region building that culminated in the inauguration of the 15-km combined bridge and tunnel in 2000 that today unites the landscape of Danish Sjaelland Island with Scania. Cross-border cooperation has been a key theme of the regional narratives, however, this narrative has shifted from optimism to highlighting the enormous strain caused by the political events of recent years (Sohn 2023). Many regional narratives relate to the development of business, innovation, and infrastructure across the border whereas the questions related with history and memory politics are nearly absent from the narratives describing the region and its landscapes (see, however, Svensson & Nilson 2023, as well as Eskilsson & Högdahl 2009 on how the ambition to commercialize cultural heritage occasionally brings forward conflicting national portrayals of history, such as when the utilization and portrayal of the 17th century rebellious Snapphane movement as freedom fighters in the context of the Swedish-Danish war that led to the 1858 border that exists to this day can be seen as a counterweight to established Swedish historiography, something that makes the story threatening to the national self-image as well as to the local identity construction. There are also scholarly narratives reflecting how natural environment (physical landscape) of Scania is different from the rest of Sweden. For instance, Germundsson cites the prominent Swedish 19th century author August Strindberg, who said when returning from the continent of Scania that it was a “completely foreign landscape for a stay-at-home Swede from up-country” and the early 19th century estate owner R.H Stjernsvärd who said of Scania that it is attached as to Sweden is a small patch of land, “to show Sweden what the rest of Europe looks like” (Germundsson 2008: 157). This focus on Scania as a different landscape is interlinked with constructions of regional heritage (Germundsson 2013). Another narrative theme of interest is how urban landscape perceptions are shaped by cities facing each other across the distance and closeness of the water that simultaneously constitutes a border (Torcelli 2012).

Danish-German border

The Danish-German borderland stretch from the North Sea West Coast to the Baltic Sea in the East. An important institutionalized historical narrative of the region tells how since the mid-19th century and with the slow dissolution of the Danish conglomerate state, a proper state border was established involving the people in a plebiscite in 1920. The narrative discusses how the border had shifted from the northern border of the medieval Holy Roman Empire at the Eider river (documented in 811) to the north of the historical region Schleswig after the war with Prussia and Austria in 1864 to its current location, dividing the former duchy of Schleswig into a northern part, belonging to Denmark and called Sønderjylland, and a southern part, belonging to Germany, and which is today part of the German federal state Schleswig-Holstein. The historical narrative of the establishment of the border in the middle is closely connected with the narrative of the border landscape as conflict-ridden. This narrative underlines how the conflict-ridden region has developed into a model region for reconciliation in Europe. It is also important to notice that today several versions of modern history exist, some underlining problems with the model region interpretations, and thus sometimes even articulating conflicting interpretations of regional history. In recent years, both Danish and German historiography have tried to move away from their nationally determined history writing to reconsider the region's importance as an integrated space, rather than just the periphery of two states – and in the Danish case, a region, which was since the 19th century assigned huge importance for the national identifications (Daubjerg 2014; Frandsen 2022).

The narrative of socially integrated national minorities forms another key narrative of the borderland and its landscape. It is also important to mention that the drawing of the 1920 border produced two national minorities that are still recognized by the respective states, the German minority on the Danish side of the border and the Danish minority on the German side. The regional narrative highlights that both minorities are

today well established in the region at political, educational and cultural institutional level, even when their struggle to achieve recognition have not been easy, especially not for the German minority because of the German occupation of Denmark in WW2 and the Nazi affiliation of many German minority members during the occupation (Klatt 2024).

What is largely absent from the public regional narratives of the border landscape, however, is the perspective of the natural heritage of the region. The landscape is diverse with the Frisian Wadden Sea and its rich marshlands in the West, a midland characterized by poor, sandy soil and the hilly landscape of the East formed by ice-age glaciers and their moraines. This division has created different East-West nature and cultural landscape settings, which were divided north-south by the national border of 1920.

Some museums have carried out historiographical research around the region's natural-cultural heritage, focusing on the influence of shipping and trade on the region's West coast (Wadden Sea area) throughout history (Wollmer et al 2001). This historiographical tradition rarely intersects with and influences the mainstream historiographical research mentioned above.

Bulgaria-Greek border

The Bulgarian border landscape, historically connected to three neighboring countries, Bulgaria, Turkey and Greek, has been studied from different perspectives. The border area was conquered by the Ottoman Turks in the mid-14th century A.D., having previously been part of the Bulgarian state and the Byzantine Empire at different times. During the Ottoman period, the border region was integrated into the Ottoman Empire, where the free movement of people and trade led to a significant mixing of different ethnic and religious groups. The narratives highlight different identities and ethnic belongings of border communities and coexistence of the three nations. Another important border narrative portrays how the borderland formed a physical border between the Eastern and Western blocs. This in-betweenness of the landscape resulted from a series of historical events, the establishment of the communist regime in Bulgaria in 1944 and the accession of Greek and Turkey to NATO in 1952.

Narratives of migration, minorities and cultural conflicts in the borderlands remind about the historical tensions between the Bulgarian Christian population and the Muslims in the region. Under communist rule (1944-1989), the Muslim population faced heavy repression, including forced name changes and strict controls on religious practices. An important popular narrative is the repressions during the communist era and how the relations between the minorities and majority have been formed and how this has shaped the borderland landscape and mindscapes (e.g., Benovska-Sabkova & Nedin 2016; Dragostinova 2016). Many sites and places are connected with memories of the attempts to assimilate the Bulgarian Muslims (sometimes called Pomaks; Neuburger 2000; Benovska-Sabkova, 2006).

Some popular landscape narratives also relate to regional economies and livelihoods. The border region was once heavily reliant on tobacco farming, a sector supported by the state during the communist era. However, following the fall of the regime, tobacco production has significantly declined due to its labor-intensive nature, low profitability, and unpredictable weather conditions. There is also a new narrative framing in which the development of Bulgaria relates to the European Union, underlining new cross-border connections between the neighboring countries (Колев, 2008). A narrative of cross-border cooperation is visible in the border landscape and shapes the meaning of the borderland. Benovska-Sabkova and Nedin (2016: 25-26) write that Bulgarian EU-internal "borders have transformed themselves into bridges". The full Schengen membership of Bulgaria since 1st of January 2025 provides new opportunities that will continue to transform the border landscape in powerful ways.

Border landscape as people's heritage

Few studies systematically focus on borderland people's landscape narratives or even less concerning how landscape narratives inform us about perceptions of Europe and Europeanness. This absence of landscape narratives from the perspective of people living in borderlands as well as how perceptions of Europe may be manifested in the landscape narratives of borderlands calls out for more in-depth examination.

B-SHAPES research offers new knowledge and understanding about the ways in which border landscape and landscape transitions are perceived by people living and crossing borders. It sheds light on borderland heritage as people's heritage rather than just heritage which is institutionally recognized and commemorated. In border regions, more mundane, everyday life narratives of border obstacles and crossings often live side by side with official historical writings of battles and divisions. Studying people's heritage necessitates asking people about meaningful places and elements of their lived landscape, places that may not be officially recognized as worth protecting but are important for personal heritage. This offers knowledge about possible conflicts over heritage in borderlands and about who should take responsibility for the preservation of the natural and cultural sites and elements currently visible or silenced in the border landscape. What conceptions and memories of borders exist among different groups of border inhabitants? Do perceptions differ on different sides of the border and among different generations, young and senior people? Is there "our" heritage and nature and "theirs", or our common heritage and inheritance?

People's perceptions of officially recognized and commemorated heritage sites are often explained by their own heritage and identity narratives and not merely the site or place attributed (Poria et al. 2006; 2003). Thus, by employing the "narratives from the ground" approach and with its focus on change agents, B-SHAPES research offers a novel, more dynamic, diverse, and versatile understanding of borders as heritage. The focus on the individual stories of citizens living in the borderland's sheds light on the importance of the borderlands' cultural and natural environment. The starting point for our research is that the meaning of border landscapes is constructed not only in relation to present day border politics but also the history and future of the border area simultaneously present in the heritage-making (Andersen & Prokkola 2021). It is therefore crucial not just to explore how heritage is constructed in borderlands but also what memorization and heritage-making does; what identities and futures it encourages and what memories are present and what are absent or silenced (Whitehead et al. 2019).

Local, borderland citizens experiences and memory cannot be separated from the institutionalized narratives of the border as heritage, the past, present and future of border landscapes; rather, the two are inextricably connected. Public narratives of the border landscape as heritage are often part of the consciousness of people who are living in the border region, however, some narratives can be unfamiliar and even unknown to many groups of people in the region, or they can have different connotations in the minds of people. Therefore, to understand how people perceive and value border landscapes as heritage it is crucial to study place-based narratives and "narrative commitments" of people living on different sides of the borders and belonging to different generations (see Wyrda 2018). The perceptions of border landscapes as heritage among different groups of people can be more diverse and versatile than what the existing history writings and heritage projects suggest.

The research offers new knowledge and understanding about the ways in which border landscape and landscape transitions are perceived by people living and crossing borders. It sheds light on borderland heritage as people's heritage rather than just heritage which is institutionally recognized and commemorated. In border regions, more mundane, everyday life narratives of border obstacles crossings must often live side

by side with official historical writings of battles and divisions. To study people's heritage necessitates asking people about their meaningful places and elements of landscape there are that are not officially recognized as worth protecting but are important for personal heritage. This offers knowledge of possible conflicts over heritage in borderlands and who should take responsibility for the preservation of the meaningful natural and cultural sites and elements visible/currently silences in the border landscape. What memories and conceptions of borders are among different groups of border inhabitants? How do perceptions differ at different sites of the border and by different generations, young and older people? Is there “our heritage and nature and theirs, or our common heritage and inheritance?”

People’s perceptions of heritage and heritage sites are often explained by their personal experiences and heritage, not merely the attributes and stories of the site or place officially recognized and highlighted (Poria *et al.* 2006; 2003). Thus, by employing the ‘narratives from the ground’ approach and with its focus on change agents, the researchers opened space for novel, dynamic, diverse, and versatile understandings of border landscapes as heritage and focused on the stories of people living in the borderlands, thus shedding light to the importance of the borderlands’ cultural and natural environment. An important starting point for research was an understanding that the meaning of border landscapes is constructed not only in relation to present day border politics but also the history and future of the border are simultaneously present in the heritage-ization (Andersen & Prokkola 2021). It is therefore crucial not just to explore how heritage is constructed in borderlands but also what memorization and heritage-making does; what identities and futures it encourages and what memories are present and what are absent or silenced (Whitehead *et al.* 2019).

Local experiences and memory cannot be separated from the institutionalized narratives of the border in past, present and future; rather, the two are inextricably connected. Public narratives of the border landscape as heritage are often part of the consciousness of people who are living in the border region, however, some narratives can be unfamiliar and unknown to many groups of people in the region, or they can have different connotations in the mind of people. Some public narratives can be also rejected. Therefore, to understand how people perceive and value border landscapes as heritage it is crucial to study place-based narratives and “narrative commitments” of people living on different sides of the borders and belonging to different generations (see Wyrda 2018). The perceptions of border landscapes as heritage among different groups of people can be more diverse and versatile than what the existing history writings and heritage projects suggest.

B-SHAPES research offers a multidimensional perspective to border heritage by shedding light on border heritage as people’s heritage and not merely a heritage which is institutionally recognized and sedimented, as well as the connections between the two. The people’s heritage perspective, often interlinked with digitalization of heritage, can be seen as a process of democratizing European memory institutions (see Lyon & Miller 2001). The open access, digitized StoryMaps produced in the research, support the process of democratizing the heritage of border landscapes.

Research process, material and methods

Borderwalk as a method

To study border landscapes as people's heritage B-SHAPES researchers developed a method and research technique called "borderwalk". The Borderwalk method is inspired by landscape walks and other mobile walking conversations and ethnographic methods that are increasingly used in social science, humanities, and human geography. Such methods add qualitative value to data compared to more traditional interview and focus group conversation techniques that often take place in offices and other institutional settings (O'Neill & Roberts 2020; Duedahl 2020). The borderwalk method is well suited for a place-based study of borders and environment as it facilitates stories and different perceptions (Jones *et al.* 2008; Macpherson 2016). Besides the usual question of moderating a focus group discussion, the borderwalk research activity requires careful planning of technical equipment, route and rhythm of the outdoor walk (Macpherson 2016). Two techniques were combined (in preference to the latter): the "standard" technique where the route is predefined by the researcher and the "go-along" technique where interviewees select the route of the walk (see Jones *et al.* 2008). Go-along techniques are especially fruitful for engaging participants, the border citizens, in the planning and design phase of research.

The borderwalk method is beneficial for studying local perceptions also because it allows a more equal relation between the interviewee and interviewed compared with many formal settings (Jones *et al.* 2008). With this method, it is possible to gain new understanding and knowledge about border landscapes and what people perceived meaningful places and sites. By walking and talking about the border landscape, access can be gained to stories that might otherwise remain invisible. Part of this is because the physical presence of material and sensory things can stir memories, which are important for people's ability to, not just perceive and remember, but also to tell stories about the landscapes (see also Andersen *et al.* 2025). Walking methods involving groups also set the stage for dialogical communication where one individual's personal experiences can enter a social space and thereby be absorbed into stories with significance for more than just the individual herself. When walking in groups, people help each other construct new narratives together, adapting their own stories to those of others and collaboratively telling stories with collective importance. Walking in the landscape is thus "an ideal technique for exploring issues around people's relationship with space" (Jones *et al.* 2008: 2-4) such a border space and landscape.

To prepare and test the borderwalk research method and activity, we implemented two pilot studies. The first pilot study was organized in Tornio-Haparanda in February 2024 by the University of Oulu research team. The second pilot study was conducted together with all partners in Ivaylovgrad close to the Bulgarian-Greek border in February 2024. The pilot study in Ivaylovgrad was crucial for developing the borderwalk research activity and generating the final plan of how to successfully integrate the citizen science approach to borderwalk research in a coherent manner, considering the differences between the border regions and age groups (youth, seniors). The careful preparation and testing of the method pointed out that importance of paying attention to gender balance in both groups, young and seniors.

Figure 1. The pilot studies took place in Tornio-Haparanda and Ivaylovgrad in February 2024 (photo by Jakola).

Altogether 42 borderwalks were conducted by WP5 partner organizations between April-October 2024 (Table 1). The borderwalks were carried in small groups. The size of the borderwalks groups varied between 1-10 participants; however, the most common number of participants was 3-4. In total, 174 people participated in the borderwalk research activity of which 94 were young people (16-31) and 80 seniors (61+).

Table 1. The number of borderwalks conducted in the four border regions.

Partner/border region	Number of borderwalks conducted	Number of people involved (youth/seniors)	Gender balance (women/men) assumed	Go-along/ Hybrid
UOULU/FI-SE	12	43 (24/19)	24/19	-/12
SDU/DK-DE	10	60 (46/14)	37/23	10/-
HH/SE-DK	8	44 (11/33)	27/17	2/6
HISTORYMUS/BG-GR	12	27 (13/14)	14/13	12/-
In total	42	174 (94/80)	79/59	24/18

The groups had been instructed beforehand, and they usually had planned the route and the sites before the actual walking activity started. The conducted borderwalks followed either go along or hybrid method, combining the go-along with the standard approach where researcher selects some sites and routes, and took place mostly in the immediate surroundings of the participants' daily environment. In the hybrid setting, the borderwalk included some standardized elements such as a pre-selected site (Tornio River at the FI-SE border) or location where the walks took place (ferry at the SE-DK and DK-DE borders). During the walks we visited a

few sites in the surrounding area selected by the group. The sites that were selected and visited related to local culture or nature, a building or other site that stands out from the landscape.

The design of the borderwalks varied based on the mobility means; while most of the borderwalks were conducted by foot, there were also several borderwalks conducted on ferry/boat emphasizing the natural landscape and water element as a border. While a ferry in the Öresund borderland context is a large moving border-crossing infrastructure with a set route, borderwalk participants chose and directed the route taken on the ferry, where researchers following the go-along method accompanied them as they explored the places and compartments of the ferry including the outer and inner decks, the lounge, and the key points of consumer centrism such as the shop, the café and the restaurant.

Except for those borderwalks conducted on ferry, participants decided the starting location by themselves. The groups were instructed to select 3-4 sites for their borderwalk but the guidelines were applied and adjusted according to the borderwalk group in question and their preferences. In the sites, we asked the participants to tell us why they had chosen the place and what kind of views and valuations they had concerning the place and its surroundings as well as whether it should be preserved and protected for future generations. In each site, we asked the participants why the site in question is meaningful, as follows:

- Where are we now, what is this place?
- Are there any specific stories related to this site? Historical. Everyday.
- Why did you select this place?
- What would be lost if this place would not be here, would it not exist?

The discussion was not restricted to the above-mentioned questions but followed a free dialogue. The discussion dynamics varied significantly between different groups. The researchers took pictures of the selected sites for further use in StoryMaps. Participants were also given the opportunity to take pictures by themselves. The interviews were recorded with the permission of the participants. The researcher also took pictures of the sites. The total duration of the research task was approximately 1,5 hours (ranging from 30 min to 4 hours). After the borderwalk, the tape-recorded conversations were transcribed and pseudonymized. The recorded interview material from borderwalks was transcribed in the original language. In few occasions strong wind and traffic noises affected the quality of the recordings and these needed to be left out of the transcriptions.

Based on the data collected during the borderwalks, we have created digital Story Maps with the ArcGIS Online StoryMap program. To design the maps, we asked for feedback from our participants. In the Finnish-Swedish borderland we also organized twelve StoryMap workshops in which participants were able to share their views on collected material (transcribed recordings and pictures) and select the sites and stories that should be included in the story map. Researchers produced story maps with ArcGIS Online StoryMap program based on the plan created in the workshop.

Figure 2. Urban border landscape in Haparanda (SE)-Tornio (FI) twin city (photo by Jakola).

Figure 3. Natural border landscape from Pekanpää (FI) village side at the Tornio River (photo by Jakola).

For recruiting participants, various methods were used (emailing, calling, on site visits, advertising in Facebook groups or local newspapers, utilization of existing contacts, as well as ad hoc on-site recruiting). The recruitment of the participation was based on the criteria that the participant 1) belongs to a group of young people (16-30 years) or to a senior group (61+), 2) who lives or works in the border area, and 3) walking outdoor is a normal everyday activity for the participant. The second and third criteria were applied on a few occasions for practical and feasibility reasons. For instance, one borderwalk group in Danish-German border region consist of persons living further away but who grew up at the border region. Also, interviews on Greek were conducted in Thessaloniki which locates further away from the Greek-Bulgarian border. The youth groups were mostly recruited through local high schools and senior groups were mostly recruited through local heritage organizations or other local associations. Recruiting participants from specific target groups turned out to be the most challenging issue. We encountered difficulties to recruit youth both from Sweden and particularly from Denmark (the Swedish-Danish border case) and from Greek, despite the use of multiple

outreach methods, including emails, phone calls, and advertisements. To secure the representation of the target groups, researchers needed to use their personal contacts, either to have contact with the individual teachers or directly to participants. The aim of the WP5 research was to conduct borderwalks on both sides of the border and have a balanced representation of the national division of borderwalk groups from both sides but citizenship was not a criterion for recruiting participants and it was not asked during the research process.

First, NVivo Transcription software was used to help with transcribing the parts of the interviews together with manual review and editing. The software does not recognize mixing of different languages which was case especially for interviews conducted in Danish-German and Swedish-Danish border regions. Also, people's casual spoken language, different dialects and sporadic low quality of the recording hampered the use of the automatized software.

Production of StoryMaps

Several techniques and methods have been used to organize and select the borderwalk material for producing the StoryMaps. Story maps are Internet-based maps which combine interactive elements, multimedia content (text, photos, video, and audio) and different ways to visualize both qualitative and quantitative material. StoryMaps enable effective storytelling on different societal and environmental topics. They are visually appealing and easy to use with different devices such as computers, tablets and smartphones (Vojteková et al. 2021) what make them accessible to a wider audience. They are therefore an effective means for scientific communications and engaging users with scientific research (Esohe et al. 2019).

We have created four (4) digital StoryMaps, one from each case border regions. The maps consist of textual narratives and pictures collected during the borderwalk research activity. To design the maps, each research team has compiled the research material obtained with the borderwalks. Three different strategies were used for selecting stories for the StoryMaps: 1) researcher selection, 2) participant consultation and 3) StoryMap workshops. The StoryMaps created from the Finnish-Swedish are based on workshops and researcher selection, The Danish-German maps are based on participant consultation and StoryMap workshops and Swedish-Danish and Bulgarian-Greek are based on researcher selection. In all cases, the transcribed material was pre-organized, and some pre-selections were made based on common criteria.

The selection of the little stories of the four StoryMap, is based on the principle of an open text (Creswell 2012). This means that that a narrative should be detached from the narrator and the researcher and open for interpretation so that everyone can relate to it and be able to read and understand the final digital StoryMaps. Stories were chosen to showcase the diverse experiences of borderland life, ranging from routine everyday interactions to moments of cultural and historical significance. All stories conformed to the narrative research criteria of coherent utterances and good stories, that is they are illustrative and understandable to a broader audience. The stories offer diverse perspectives on youth and senior participants. The pictures were chosen mostly based on quality, and suitability of motive. Thematically, the StoryMaps' "little stories" relate to the border and border landscape where the research activity took place, but some relate to discussion of European borders and borderlands more broadly. The StoryMaps thereby illustrate how the borders are part of the environment and landscape of local people and what they value and consider meaningful. StoryMaps can be read as specific border landscape narratives co-created by researchers and the border citizens. The University of Oulu team is responsible for the technical implementation of the StoryMaps using Environmental Service Research Institute's (ESRI) Web-based GIS platform, ArcGIS Online.

Ethical considerations

The Code of Ethics and Code of Conduct of B-SHAPES project has been carefully throughout in the planning and implementation of research activities. Before starting the research activity, all partners completed the personal data ethics issue checklist that was approved by the B-SHAPES ethical committee. The informed consent procedures and data protection procedures have been followed carefully as determined in the projects Code of Ethics and Code of Conduct.

General instructions were created regarding the implementation and instruction of participants. Some groups were given info sessions before the actual borderwalk, some were instructed beforehand by other means (such as by emails) and others were instructed right before the borderwalk started (Figure 4). Info sessions were held particularly with school groups. In case instructions and ethical forms were given only before the borderwalk, participants were given enough time to carefully read through the documents and raise possible questions, as well as to discuss the sites participants wish to visit during the borderwalk.

The participants who were recruited to take part in the borderwalk and StoryMap research activity were informed about the research, and they have been given an opportunity to ask questions about the researchers. They were informed about their right to refuse to participate in the study or interrupt it without justifying it. They were informed that there are no consequences for you from participating in the study, refusing to participate, or suspending participation. They were informed that participating in the study may not benefit them personally. They were informed that research material is treated confidentially in all situations and that the data collected is used to conduct scientific research. They were informed that the results presented in the study cannot be used to determine the data of an individual participant, as the names of all participants are changed to numeric identifiers. They were informed that the material will be processed in accordance with the privacy notice provided to them. They were told that the data will be used to produce digitalized StoryMaps. The personal data to be combined with the research data will be destroyed five years after completing the data collection. The participants have given their consent to ensure that the material collected during the research activities can be used in the Story Maps.

To protect participant privacy all material was pseudonymized. Direct personal identifiers were replaced with generic descriptors and indirect personal information were generalized or omitted. The coding of the interviews was done on a group level (GROUP 1/2/3...) with affiliation to target group (youth/seniors) and country (SE/DK/DE/FI/BG/GR). Borderwalk participants do not have individual codes, but different voices are separated by indicating participants (participant 1, participant 2 etc.).

Figure 4. All participants were handed an information sheet and a privacy notice in their own language. The participants signed an informed consent letter before the research activity started (photo by Jakola).

StoryMaps of the border regions

Finnish-Swedish border region

Figure 5. The Tornio River (photo by Jakola).

Short description of the area

The Finnish-Swedish border area is one of the internal border regions of the EU. This sparsely populated northern European border region shares a common history and has a long tradition of cross-border interaction and cooperation. Historically, the region has formed a culturally, economically and politically united region from the 11th century until the beginning of the 19th century. At that time, the Kingdom of Sweden ceded Finland to the Russian Empire in the Treaty of Hamina in 1809. The new border was drawn along the Tornio and Muonio rivers and divided into the villages and communities built around these rivers which traditionally had formed a route to the Arctic Sea. In the Tornio River Valley, people originally spoke Finnish dialect Meänkieli (“our language”) which is nowadays acknowledged as a minority language in Sweden. In addition, the northernmost part of the border region is part of the Sami region (covering areas from northern Finland, Sweden, Norway, and Kola peninsula in Russia) as well. The Sami are the only indigenous people within the European Union, and they have their own self-government and minority status in each country.

Even though the border area has experienced geopolitical tensions and changes during the 20th century such as Finland gaining independence in 1917 after being an autonomous Grand Duchy of Russia for more than hundred years, strict regulations of cross-border mobility during the WWs and being a frontier between West and East during the Cold War period, both formal and everyday interactions across the border have remained active and vivid. Both local level cooperation and Nordic ministry level cooperation have played a significant role in this; for instance, the exemption of passport requirements between the Nordic countries was introduced in 1957.

Sweden and Finland joined the EU in 1995, which strengthened the institutionalization of local and regional co-operation. Especially the advanced cross-border co-operation initiatives of Tornio (FIN)-Haparanda (SWE)

twin city have gained scholarly, policy and media attention. Due to the integrated nature of the region in terms of cross-border commuting and daily interaction, the border closures introduced as a response to the COVID-19 pandemic were considered highly problematic from the perspective of local people. There are various ongoing cross-border cooperation projects including a project investigating needed policy and legislative changes on how to secure free cross-border mobility and interaction in the future.

Implementation of the borderwalks and the StoryMap

UOulu conducted altogether 12 borderwalks at the Swedish-Finnish border area within period May 30 – June 28, 2024 (see Table 12). Six borderwalks were conducted with youth groups (4 in Finland and 2 in Sweden) and six border walks with senior groups (3 in Finland and 3 in Sweden). Of all borderwalks, 10 (GROUPS 1-10) took place in the urban border landscape of Tornio(FI)-Haparanda(SE) twin city, while two (GROUPS 11-12) were carried out in a natural border landscape of Pekanpää (FI) and Vittangi (SE) rural villages locating across each other's further north in the Tornio River Valley. Altogether 43 people participated in the research activity, of which 24 were young people and 19 seniors. 15 students studied in a Finnish school and 9 in a Swedish school; the slight imbalance between the numbers is explained by the class sizes and that's for, independent of researchers. Of 19 seniors, 10 participated to the research activity from Finland and 9 from Sweden. Regarding the gender balance, 24 participants were women (assumed) and 19 men (assumed). Of all 12 borderwalk groups, 10 were mixed groups and two included only women (assumed) indicating good overall gender balance within the groups (Table 2).

Borderwalk GROUPS1-10 were conducted as a hybrid method in which both participants and researchers chose sites. The pre-selected site for borderwalks was Tornio River. The participants selected both historical and everyday sites of which most of them were cultural sites and only a few represented the natural environment. Moreover, there were no significant differences between youth and seniors in terms of selecting different sites. Target groups selected sites which were both part of the more dominant historical narrative of the border landscape (such as bridges, monuments, common market square) and everyday sites which have been meaningful for them (such as beaches, places of entertainment). However, in selection of Finnish youths, the everyday sites were emphasized more. While the borderwalk GROUPS 1-10 followed the general walking design introduced above, the senior borderwalk GROUPS 11-12 with local fishermen/-women were conducted in applied manner due to practical reasons² and the discussions were entailed mainly on the border river and its meaningfulness for the local people.

As for the language, borderwalk GROUPS 1-4, 7-9, 11-12 were conducted in Finnish which is also the native language of both researchers. The participants of "Swedish" senior GROUPS 9 and 12 were bilingual, which enabled conducting the interviews in Finnish/Meänkieli. The borderwalk GROUP5 was conducted in Swedish and with GROUP6 both Swedish and English was used. Due to limited oral Swedish skills of another researcher, in GROUP6 youth participants talked Swedish and researcher used both English and Swedish. Participants appeared to be comfortable with the situation as their English listening skills seemed to be very sufficient. One of the participants even preferred to answer in English as well. A few of the participants in GROUP6 were also bilingual and they used Finnish words occasionally, but so limited extent that the conversation was accessible also for non-Finnish-speaking participants.

² Due to the practical reasons related to limited space in fishing boats and special code of conducts related to the fishing turns and queuing, GROUP 11 was interviewed at the riverbank and GROUP12 was divided into two sections. Interviewee join the fishing boat with two participants and one participant was interviewed at the border.

Table 2. The borderwalk groups conducted in the Finnish-Swedish border.

Borderwalk code	Target group	Starting location	No. of participants	Gender F/M (assumed)	Mobility	Date
GROUP 1	Youth	Tornio/FI	5	3/2	Walking	30.4.2024
GROUP 2	Youth	Tornio/FI	3	3/0	Walking	30.4.2024
GROUP 3	Youth	Tornio/FI	3	2/1	Walking	2.5.2024
GROUP 4	Youth	Tornio/ FI	5	2/3	Walking	2.5.2024
GROUP 5	Youth	Haparanda/ SE	4	2/2	Walking	21.5.2024
GROUP 6	Youth	Haparanda/ SE	5	2/3	Walking	21.5.2024
GROUP 7	Senior	Tornio/FI	3	2/1	Walking	12.6.2024
GROUP 8	Senior	Tornio/FI	3	1/2	Walking	12.6.2024
GROUP 9	Senior	Haparanda/ SE	3	3/0	Walking	17.6.2024
GROUP 10	Senior	Haparanda/ SE	3	2/1	Walking	18.6.2024
GROUP 11	Senior	Pekanpää/ FI	4	1/3	At one location	18.6.2024
GROUP 12	Senior	Vittangi/ SE	3	1/2	Boat	18.6.2024

For selection of the sites, stories, and pictures for StoryMaps, the University of Oulu used two different methods: StoryMap workshops and researcher selection (see the general description above). Accordingly, UOulu conducted four StoryMap workshops which took place at Tornio-Haparanda area during May – August 2024. The workshops were conducted with borderwalk groups 1-10. There was one workshop with each target groups: youth in Finland (GROUP1-4), youth in Haparanda (GROUP5-6), seniors in Finland (GROUP7-8) and seniors in Haparanda (GROUP9-10). SDU organized one workshop with a youth group (GROUP 10). Each workshop lasted about 2 hours.

All workshops followed a similar design. First, researchers processed and pre-organized the interview material based on different sites. They compiled a document with all the sites and pre-selected stories. Additionally, the pictures taken during the borderwalks were organized by site and printed as physical photos for the workshops. A file with different stories was given to everyone. At the workshop, participants were instructed to select a certain number of sites and then choose stories and pictures for these sites and create StoryMap posters. Participants worked in groups of 3-5 people and all groups made their own posters which served as research material.

After the participants had selected the stories and pictures and attached them to the poster, a summary discussion was held. These discussions were recorded, and it was underlined for the participants that in this phase participants can tell more stories or reflections related to the sites. Moreover, these additional stories can be selected from these recordings for the StoryMaps (see researchers' selection below). This was the case especially for those selected sites with only one story from the borderwalk.

Following Biggs *et al.* (1995) different participation modes (contractual, consultative, collaborative and co-creative), the participation level within StoryMap workshops could be defined as an intermediate form of collaborative and co-creative. Although the onsite workshop design enabled an active agency of participants and their independent working, the workshop structure was usually researcher led. Due to the limited time resources for the workshop (only 2 hours), the structure and instructions were given by the researcher. However, the level of activity and participation varied between target groups.

In senior workshops participants negotiated more about the meaning of the different sites and stories. Also, in other senior workshop participants wanted to separate some of the stories as their own site/category. Whereas youth operated more straightforwardly – usually one person suggested some site and/or story and others agreed. In that moment it was usually relatively challenging for the youth participants to put into words and justify why did they wanted to choose a certain story. They were usually just considered as “good ones”. However, in the recorded summary discussions where participants presented their posters and selections, more justifications were given. The workshop groups also choose 1-3 photos for each site. It was common for them to use both visuality and content as a justification for their selection. Although participants worked in two groups in the workshops (except workshop 4 had only one group), the posters were very similar as there was only a little variation in their selection. On a general level, it could be concluded that both youth and senior groups selected sites which are mostly commonly known and meaningful for a wider audience, not only for them personally. While selected stories represented both institutionalized and more personal everyday stories related to these sites. The digital StoryMaps (see below) were created based on the workshop posters (see Figure 6) and additional stories selected by the UOulu researchers.

Figure 6. A StoryMap poster created by the participants. (Photo by Jakola)

Table 3. The selected sites for the StoryMap from the Finnish-Swedish border region.

FI-SE border	Swedish side	Finnish side
Victoria's square	Haparanda railway station	Pikisaari (beach)
Border line	Military bunkers from WWI	Museum of Tornio Valley
Tornio River	Photographer Mia Green's park	Pohja sport stadium
The railway bridge	Old water tower	Kojamo salmon statue
Kukkolarapids	Hermansons	Rantakatu (street with old wooden buildings)
Tornio riverbanks	Tull park's area and view	
Sovereignty islands	Haparanda beach	
Tornio-Haparanda travel center	War child monument	
Tornio riverbanks	Haparanda market square	
	Bilingual city signs	
	Tar depot	
	Old store in Vittangi	

Victoria's Square

Tutkija: *Miksi me ollaan nyt tulleet?*

Osaillistuja: *Victoriantorille*

Tutkija: *Mikä paikka tämä on?*

Osaillistuja: *Raja*

(In English)

Researcher: *Where are we now?*

Participant: *At Victoria's square*

Tornio Riverbank

Tutkija: *Mites sitten nämä jokirannat, onko niillä ominaispiirteitä, Suomen ja Ruottin puolelta?*

Osaillistuja 1: *Tailla on ainakin Suomen puolella raparperit*

Osaillistuja 2: *Joo, tuo on vähän semmonen mikämpi tuo Ruottin puoli*

Osaillistuja 1: *Sievempät tuo ranta.*

Osaillistuja 2: *Se on sievempäs, ja kun Suomen puoli on matalampaa, Ruutti on semmonen mikämpi ja paljon hienempi. Ja siellä on aina huolehdittu niistä rakennuksista aina paremmin kuin Suomen puolella. Siellä on aina nimko siitä nämä paikat ja on aina huolehdittu niistä vanheistakin rakennuksista, ja on luttettu katto jos on huonot, ladotus ja kaakius... Suomen puolelta ne on sitten paljon huonommin hoidettu*

Osaillistuja1: *Ja Ruottin rantaahan on semmonen että siellähan ei ole ilta-suurinbo*

(In English)

Figure 7. Screenshots illustrating the final digitalized Finnish-Swedish border region StoryMap.

Danish-German border region

Figure 8. The Danish-German dike located at the West coast of the region (photo by Andersen).

Short description of the area

The Danish-German borderlands stretch from the North Sea West Coast to the Baltic Sea in the East. Since the mid-19th century and with the slow dissolution of the Danish conglomerate state, a proper state border was established, yet it has shifted from the north of the historical region Schleswig to its current location in the middle, dividing the region into a north, belonging to Denmark and called Sønderjylland, and a south, belonging to Germany, and which is today part of the German federal state Schleswig-Holstein. Because of its history, the region is often seen as conflict-ridden, developing into a model region for reconciliation, yet several versions of this modern history exist sometimes even articulating conflicting interpretations.

In 1973, Denmark joined the then European Economic Community and was included into the custom union and since then, the German side close to the border has been heavily influenced by cross-border shopping of Danes in Germany. Since Denmark's entrance into Schengen in 1999, the border has been open, yet it was temporarily closed since January 2016 for a long range of reasons, among others the COVID-19 pandemic. Somewhat controversial is it that an almost 70 km fence designed to protect the Danish pig industry from infections from the African pigs' disease, was erected by the Danish government on this border in 2019 and is still in place. This is the first time in history that the state border is physically marked in almost its entirety.

Implementation of borderwalks and the StoryMap

The SDU team conducted altogether 10 borderwalks in the Danish-German border region within time period May-September 2024. Six of the borderwalks groups were conducted with youth and four with seniors, each group consisting of from 3 to 10 people. Altogether 60 participants participated in the borderwalk research activity of which 46 were young people and 14 seniors. The slight imbalance between two generational target groups is explained by the sizes of the participated school classes and thus,

independent from the researcher. Regarding the gender division, 37 of the participants were women (assumed) and 23 men (assumed) indicating a relatively good gender balance. GROUP 3 was a mixed group of both Danish and German seniors, GROUP 4 and GROUP 5 were students from the German minority high school in Aabenraa, Denmark, GROUP 10 consisted of students from the Danish minority high school in Flensburg, Germany and many students in the high school in Tønder, Denmark, came from or lived in Germany, thus underlining the complexity of national belonging characterizing the region.

A relatively short 70-kilometer-long land border enabled covering almost the entire border area from the West to the East during research activity. Also, both the East and the West were represented by one sailing trip as well. Although a part of the inner landscape in the region, that is, the parts further away from the sea on both sides, were not covered, the spatial coverage was much higher compared to other empirical border regions and offers a comprehensive investigation in border landscapes with different natural and cultural features. Thus, borderwalks took place in varying geographical locations where some were connected mainly to the region's historical narrative (see above), while others connected more to the everyday activities of the interlocutors, including leisure activities. Five of the borderwalks started from the Danish side of the border (GROUP 1, 4, 5, 6, 7), only 2 from the German (GROUP 3 and 10), whereas additionally 3 walks started from a border crossing point and hence at the location of the state border itself (GROUP 2, 8, 9). Eight of the borderwalks were conducted on foot (GROUPS 2, 4) and two with on a ferry (GROUP 3 and 6). GROUP 3 took place in the East at the Flensburg fjord between Flensburg (DE) and Sønderborg (DK) with mix of Danish and German seniors, while GROUP 6 was organized at the islands on the West coast and covered both Rømø (DK) and Sylt (DE), as well as a ferry ride in-between.

All walks were go-along, where the interlocutors chose the narrated sites, yet one 'walk' took place on a boat and here it was the researcher that chose the boat trip but the interlocutors who chose the site narrated on the trip. The sites selected were mostly related to the region's historical narrative (see above), or they referred very explicitly to everyday life and personal experiences crossing the state border. The former type of stories was very significant among the 60+ generation and the latter characterized the younger generation's stories more. The younger generation was also more engaged with leisure activities in the landscape.

As for the language, both Danish and German was used as story-telling language, according to the wishes of the interlocutors as well as the researcher conducting the walks. As many of the interlocutors were fluent in both languages, the interlocutors seemed to adjust very easily to the wishes of the researcher conducting the walks, even when the wishes were not made explicit. There was also a significant number of times when languages were constantly mixed during conversations (GROUP 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 10).

Altogether it was very easy to conduct borderwalks with the older generation, and it demanded more effort with the younger generation. The older generation came to the walks with rehearsed narratives, and many took over guiding the walks themselves. The younger generation was generally more insecure in telling stories and it was more difficult for the researcher to get the conversations going. This might also have been an effect of how the interlocutors were recruited, were the 60+ generation choose voluntarily to participate in the walks and most of the high school students were recruited through their institutions – apart from GROUP 10, which was also much more talkative.

Table 4. The borderwalk groups conducted in the Danish-German border region.

Borderwalk group code	Target group	Starting location/ Country	No. of particip.	Gender F/M (assumed)	Mobility	Date
GROUP 1	Senior	Frøslev (DK)	3	0/3	Walking/ Car	27.05.24
GROUP 2	Senior	Padborg (DK)	3	1/2	Walking	03.07.24
GROUP 3	Senior	Flensburg/DE (- Sønderburg /DK ferry)	4	3/1	Sailing	10.07.24
GROUP 4	Youth	Kollund/DK	7	2/5	Walking	20.08.24
GROUP 5	Youth	Padborg border crossing DK-DE	10	9/1	Walking	20.08.24
GROUP 6	Senior	Rømø/DK (- Sylt/DE) Ferry	4	3/1	Sailing/car/ Walking	29.08.24
GROUP 7	Youth	Marskstien border crossing DK-DE	9	6/3	Walking	30.08.24
GROUP 8	Youth	Border-crossing Sæd & Sønderløgum (DK) /Suderløgum (DE))	8	4/4	Walking	30.08.24
GROUP 9	Youth	Rudbøl(DK)/ Rosenkranz(DE) border crossing	8	6/2	Walking	30.08.24
GROUP 10	Youth	Flensburg (DE)	4	3/1	Walking	27.09.24

The stories chosen for the region’s StoryMap all relate to the border, the borderlands, the borderlandscape in one way or another. Mostly this concerns the border region investigated, but sometimes the stories even relate to European borders. The StoryMap constructed thereby illustrates how the border / borders / borderlandscape matters to people living in these borderlands and in what ways the border becomes present in the everyday lives of people. The selection of the stories followed “the open text principle” (Creswell 2018) that formed the criterial for selection in all border regions. At an overall level, and based in the findings, the “good stories” were foremost subjective (see Moen 2006), that is, based in personal experiences of the interlocutors; they were affectionate from the viewpoint of the interlocutors; many of them related to local heritage; and some were peculiar, funny and entertaining.

In the process of choosing stories, one StoryMap workshop was carried out with a youth group (group 10). The stories from group 10 are thus all chosen by the interlocutors. This group was very well informed about issues concerning the border region – its heritage, politics, and culture – and it was easy for them to select the sites. Other groups were asked to comment on the initial choice of stories made by the researcher, and

the material was then sorted in terms of chronology. Very little material chosen by the researcher was dismissed by the interlocutors, and only a little was changed in terms of wording. The researcher thus had to make rejections herself, and she rejected almost 3/4 of the total material collected. This material is still useful for other purposes.

Table 5. The selected sites for the StoryMap from the Danish-German borderland.

At the DK-DE border	German side	Danish side
The Rømø-Sylt ferry	The Danish cultural house on Sild	Sct. Clemens Church and cemetery, Rømø
The Danish-German dike	The Music Festival	The Frøslev Internment Camp
Grüne Grenze border-crossing	The dike in Rosenkranz	The border guard monument
Border-crossing in Rudbøl/Rosenkranz	The grandfather's shop	Monument at the Padborg border
Border-crossing by Sæd	Border shop in Süder Lügum	The Customs House in Padborg
Border-crossing by Frøslev	The Isted Lion	The House at Haraldskærvej
Border-crossing by Padborg	Cross-border shopping in Wassersleben	The Border Guard Path
The Wild Boar Fence by Padborg		Shelters at the Border Guard Path
Border-crossing by Nyhus/Niehus		Annie's Kiosk
The lake by Nyhus/Niehus		The Oxe Islands
Border-crossing by Kruså		Former Sønderborg military academy
Sønderborg-Flensburg ferry		Flensburg fjord
The King's Bay		Danish and German architecture in Bov

The Danish-German stone in the West Coast
 The Stone Pavilion
 The border crossing on Rønde/Roskilde
 The Green Border, the historical border gate and the Møntz path
 The stone on New Year's Eve
 The grandfather's shop on Roskildevej
 About some border roads
 Border crossing to Søst
 Border crossing to Favrre
 The Favrre Settlement Camp
 The border guard monument
 Border crossing by Polbyg
 Monument of the Polbyg border
 The Customs House in Polbyg
 The House of Marthabønder
 The Border Guard Sign
 The Wild Boar Fence
 Border crossing by Nilsen/Søst
 The Sign to Nilsen/Søst
 Talk up the Høgebjergs Bus

Rønde-Sylt ferry

Bedstemors kusine havde en datter, der boede i Esbjerg. Men datteren, som var hunderger, kom så og boede hos sin mor på Rønde. Og så havde hun den her lille dreng på en fem- seks år. Hun fik den idé at pakke drengen med smagelyst, så hun selvby kunne sælge en masse cigaretter. Så kommer hun hen til tålløsen og tålløsen spørger om de har noget der skal fortoldes, om hun har nogle cigaretter der skal fortoldes i dag. Hun sagde, nej det har jeg ikke. Men det har jeg, sagde drengen. Det var sidste gang hun brugte ham som muslin.

(In English)

Cousin's cousin had a daughter who lived in Esbjerg. But the daughter, who was a shaman, then came and stayed with her mother on Rønde, and she had this little boy, five or six years old. She got the idea to pack the boy with contraband, so he could carry a lot of cigarettes of the ferry. Then she comes to the customs officer and the customs officer asks if they have anything that needs to be cleared, if she has any cigarettes that need to be cleared today. She said, no I haven't. But I do, said the boy. It was the last time she used him as a mule.

The Wild boar fence

Informant 1: Ja, jeg er jo medlem af SSW's ungdomsforening [SSW = det østslaviske parti]. Da vildsvinehægen var ved at blive opført, arrangerede vi [SSW ungdom] en volleyboldkamp over hegnet sammen med det tyske mindretal [de Jungen Spitzers] for at vise vores utilfredshed med hegnet. Altså, jeg var ikke med, jeg var endnu ikke med i partiet, men baret gjorde det. Det kan godt være at der er et problem med vildsvine og jagtgrænser, men det er ikke et godt signal at sende, at vi alle sådan et hegn op. Slet ikke i en region hvor der er mindretal og begge sider af grænsen. Vi havde håbet, at protesten ville have sat en stopper for opførelsen, men sådan gik det jo ikke. Jeg tror ikke vi mindretal betyder så meget for den danske regering.

Researcher: Hvorfor gør det en forskel, at der er mindretal i regionen?

Informant 2: Mange af os har jo hørt historier om had mellem danskere og tyskere fra famillemembrer. Det var jo den måde de levede på. De voksede op på. At vi ikke har problemer med hinanden i dag, er jo bare en god ting. Og der hører det ikke et begyndt at sætte hegn op igen.

Figure 9. Screenshots illustrate the final digitalized DK-DE StoryMap.

Swedish-Danish border region

Figure 10. On the ferry between Helsingør (DK) and Helsingborg (SE) (Photo by Miraka)

Short description of the area

The Oresund region, named after the narrow strait connecting the North and Baltic Seas and which also constitutes the border since 1658 and spanning parts of Denmark and Sweden. It is often defined to include Sjælland (Regions Hovedstaden and Sjælland), Skåne, and Halland, though some analyses, such as the B-SHAPES project, also include North Jutland. This addition reflects its geographic proximity to Halland, shared agricultural dominance, and popularity as a tourist destination. The landscape is characterized by water and flatlands, transitioning to forests and low mountains along its eastern edges.

The region's critical infrastructure underlines its strategic importance. This includes the well-known Copenhagen (Denmark)-Malmö (Sweden) bridge and tunnel, operational since 2000, ferry routes connecting the Danish island Bornholm with the Danish mainland via the Swedish town of Ystad, between Helsingør (DK) and Helsingborg (SE), and Copenhagen Airport, which serves as a hub for both nations. Historically, the area has witnessed shifting borders; Skåne and Halland, once Danish territories, were annexed by Sweden during the 17th century. These historical transitions continue to shape regional identity.

Danish and Swedish are languages that are closely related and mutually intelligible in written form. However, spoken comprehension often proves challenging, particularly for younger generations, reflecting subtle yet significant linguistic divides. Despite this, the Oresund region thrives as a space of cultural and economic interconnection, where the strait serves not as a barrier but as a bridge linking two nations.

The border was an external EU border between Danish accession to the EU in 1973 and Sweden's accession in 1995. Since then, it is an internal border regulated by Nordic agreements on passport free travel as well as the Schengen agreement regulations. The last decade, however, has seen both countries adopt different types of border controls in response to crises framed around migration, crime and the COVID-19 pandemic.

Implementation of the borderwalks and the StoryMap

In total, the Halmstad University team conducted eight borderwalks during period May- August in 2024; 6 with senior groups (4 with Danish seniors, 2 with Swedish seniors) and 2 with youth groups (one group with both Danish and Swedish youth). Some of the walks took place as parallel sub-walks as participants grouped together and took different routes. Altogether 44 participated in the research activity, of which 33 seniors and 11 youth. The slight imbalance in the national division between participants and target groups was due to the recruiting strategy used. Recruiting Danish seniors through advertisement in local newspaper evoked a great interest and there was no need to limit the number of participants. Furthermore, the broader engagement of Danish seniors provided the additional benefit of exposing the researchers to a richer set of Danish linguistic and cultural perspectives, balancing their pre-existing familiarity with the Swedish side.

The Halmstad University team conducted borderwalks in three different locations and borderlandscapes; on ferry between Helsingborg (SE) -Helsingør (DK) with senior and youth groups, at the historical border between Denmark and Sweden in Knäred with Swedish seniors, and in Copenhagen with Danish youth. The borderwalks covered several key locations, each with historical and cultural relevance. At the Ferry Terminal in Sweden, participants discussed the significance of the ferry connection as a daily commuter route and a link between Sweden and Denmark. In Helsingør's historic city center and also gazing from the ferry as it left land and moved closer to land, they saw Kronborg Castle from different perspectives, known for its strategic maritime role and association with Shakespeare's *Hamlet*. The ferry's role in everyday life was highlighted as an essential part of cross-border mobility, while Tura was examined as a long-standing social tradition of traveling back and forth for shopping, dining, and entertainment. Discussions on cultural and historical reflections considered how the ferry route has shaped interactions and perceptions between the two nations. In Knäred, participants walked along the old Swedish-Danish border, focusing on efforts to preserve historical markers, retracing past events through walking tours, and engaging with stories and folklore passed down through generations. In Copenhagen, the final site, discussions revolved around the city's historical ties to Sweden and its role as a modern urban hub within the Öresund region, emphasizing contemporary mobility and cross-border integration.

Borderwalk GROUP 1-6 were conducted on ferry between Helsingborg (SE)-Helsingør (DK). The ferry route was selected as a key site for the borderwalks due to its key role in shaping border interaction at the maritime border. The ferry route lies at the narrowest part of the Oresund Strait and the 20-minute ferry trip serves as the only direct crossing point for the two cities. Four of the borderwalks at the ferry (GROUP Youth/SV/Group1, Seniors/DK/Group2, Seniors/DK/Group3, Seniors/DK/Group4, Seniors/DK/Group5, Seniors/SV/Group6, Seniors/DK/Group7, Youth/DK/Group8) took place with Danish seniors, one with Danish youth and one with Swedish seniors. All borderwalks were two-way sailing trips without boarding the ferry, except one borderwalk conducted with Danish seniors on the last day which was only one way from Helsingør to Helsingborg and included half an hour walk on land in different sites. The participants later decided to continue spending their time in Helsingborg as it was their first time in the town. These borderwalks were carried out as hybrid method as the ferry itself was a standardized element decided by the researchers. However, on the ferry itself participants took the lead in walking around between different key locations and discussing memories related to the perspectives "on the other side" offered from the outer deck, the consumption centered memories awakened at the ferry shop, memories of socializing induced at the restaurant, etc. One of the borderwalks with Swedish seniors (GROUP 7) was conducted at the historical border between Denmark and Sweden in Knäred. The researchers adopted a go-along method for this walk, following a path prepared in advance by one of the participants. The borderwalk differed from others in terms of distance and duration. The walk covered approximately 15 kilometers

through challenging terrain and lasted over four hours. The borderwalk GROUP8 was conducted in Copenhagen with three young migrant residents recruited through the extended networks of researchers. A go-along method was adopted for this walk.

The borderwalks were conducted simultaneously in Swedish and Danish. The researchers spoke Swedish, while Danish participants spoke Danish. This bilingual approach highlighted the natural challenge of cross-border communication and cooperation in the region, as residents can often understand the written forms of each other's languages but struggle with spoken comprehension. This challenge was particularly evident during the walks with Danish seniors, where mutual understanding required patience and effort, reflecting the linguistic divide that persists despite the geographic proximity of the two countries. In Copenhagen (GROUP 8), there was two Swedes and one Norwegian all living in Copenhagen; thus, the borderwalk was conducted in Swedish, with participants speaking either Swedish or Norwegian. The young migrant participants spoke a mix of Danish and other languages as their first language, but many understood Swedish through exposure to Scandinavian linguistic similarities or formal education.

Table 6. The borderwalk groups conducted in the Swedish-Danish border region

Border walk group code	Target group	Starting location/ Country	No. of particip.	Gender F/M (assumed)	Mobility	Date
Group 1	Youth	Helsingborg/ Helsingør	8	4/	Walking on ferry.	14.05.2024
Group 2	Seniors	Helsingør/ Helsingborg	7	4/3	Walking in Helsingør + walking on ferry.	13.08.2024
Group 3	Seniors	Helsingør/ Helsingborg	7	6/1	Walking in Helsingør + walking on ferry.	13.08.2024
Group 4	Seniors	Helsingør/ Helsingborg	7	4/3	Walking in Helsingør + walking on ferry.	15.08.2024
Group 5	Seniors	Helsingborg/ Helsingør	8	4/4	Walking on ferry.	16.08.2024
Group 6	Seniors	Helsingør/ Helsingborg	1	1/0	Walking in Helsingør + walking in Helsingborg + walking on ferry.	16.08.2024
Group 7	Senior	Knäred/ SE	3	1/2	Walking	27.08.2024
Group 8	Youth	Copenhagen/ DK	3	3/0	Walking	21.09.2024

Table 7. The selected sites for the StoryMap from the Swedish-Danish border region. The selection was based on researchers' selection.

At the SE-DK border	At the Swedish side	At the Danish side
Ferry Promenade Deck	Ferry Terminal	Historic City Center
Ferry Restaurant	Refugee Monument	Stengade shopping street
Ferry Dutyfree Shop	Parapeten Breakwater & Marina	Ice Cream Shop
Ferry Observation Deck	The Hiking Route	Kronborg Castle
Ferry on the Border	Boundary Stone Partition	
Border-crossing Copenhagen-Malmö	The UFO stone	
The Øresund Bridge	The hill called "Danska Backen"	
View towards the Barsebäck nuclear power plant		

Ferry Terminal

Deltagare 1: Ja, det var nästan ett måste när man var yngre. Men handlade om att åka fram och tillbaka. Sedan blev det en vana på fredagar och lördagar innan man skulle ut... Sen när jag hade familj åkte vi ofta över på lördagar för att shoppa. Ja, man fyllde huset och passade på att ta något snabbt där också [att åka].

Deltagare 2: Vi åker med vår pensionsförening två gånger om året, på morgonen. Då är vi ofta 50-60 personer. Det är subventionerat, så maten är billigare.

(In English)

Participant 1: "Yes, it was almost a must when you were younger. You took turns going back and forth. Then it became a routine on Fridays and Saturdays before going out... Later, when I had a family, we often went over on Saturdays to shop. Yes, you filled the house and took the opportunity to grab something quick there as well [to eat]"

Participant 2: "We go with our pensioners' association twice a year, in the morning. Then we are often 50-60 people. It's subsidized, so food is cheaper."

The Hiking Route

Småländingarna håller sig för sig själva och hallänningarna för sig själva. Vi har haft en del kontakter över gränsen, men det är inte så vanligt. Jag och min man har brutit mönstret eftersom vi har haft djur på både sidor av gränsen har gjort det möjligt för oss att låta våra fådjursdjur. Detta kan kanske förklaras med att gränsen har varit en naturlig gränslinje, men jag tror inte att den (den danska sidan) lever kvar i vardagen är danska sommargäster här som ibland tar upp frågan. Då kan vi diskutera att den här sidan var dansk, men inte den andra.

(In English)

The people of Småland keep to themselves and the people of Halland to themselves. We have had some contacts across the border, but it is not so common. My husband and I have broken the pattern because we have had animals on both sides of the border. It has allowed us to get to know more people. This can perhaps be explained by the fact that the border has been a natural demarcation, but I don't think it the Danish way lives on in everyday life. But there are Danish summer guests here who sometimes raise the issue. Then we can discuss that this side was Danish, just not the other.

Figure 11: Screenshots illustrating the final digitalized SE-DK StoryMap

Bulgarian-Greek border region

Figure 12. Greek neighbourhood in Ivaylovgrad (BG). Greece and Turkey in the horizon (photo by Karaneshev).

Short description of the area

The Bulgarian-Greek border, extending approximately 494 kilometers from the Black Sea to the junction with North Macedonia, is a region of significant historical, geographical, and cultural importance (Figure 12). The area is characterized by diverse landscapes, including the Rhodope and Sakar Mountain ranges and the Maritsa River valley. Historically, this border region has been inhabited by various civilizations, including the ancient Greeks and Thracians, and later became part of the Roman and Byzantine empires. The region was conquered by the Ottoman Turks in the mid-14th c. A.D. Following the Balkan Wars and the subsequent changes in territorial boundaries in the early 20th century, the region experienced notable political and demographic shifts. The current border line between Bulgaria and Greece was established after the end of the First World War (1919).

The area of Western Rhodope Mountain is known for the vast presence of Muslim population who are ethnic Bulgarians, Roma and Turks. They all speak Bulgarian language, although the Turks and some of the Roma people speak Turkish as a first language. The period of communist power in Bulgaria (1944-1989) was particularly hard for the Muslim population due to the repressive assimilationist campaigns against them, known as the “Revival process”. Historically, the Eastern part of the Rhodope Mountain close to the border triangle between Bulgaria, Greece and Turkey was known for significant mixing of different ethnic and religious groups. Ethnic diversity has been reduced in the years following the end of the First World War. After the establishment of the communist regime in Bulgaria in 1944 and the joining of Greece and Turkey to NATO in 1952 this region became an actual physical border between the West and the East blocks, which resulted in the heavy presence of many troops of the Bulgarian army. This contributed to the fact that the

city of Ivaylovgrad was practically closed for external visitors – the only way to enter the city used to be only after acquiring special documents from the government and passing several military checkpoints.

Bulgaria joined European Union in 2007 and today, the Bulgarian-Greek border has become a focal point for cross-border cooperation, focusing on collaborative projects aimed at fostering economic development, environmental sustainability (such as establishment of cross-border protected areas), and cultural exchange. The latest development took place on January 1, 2025, when Bulgaria became a full member of Schengen.

Implementation of the borderwalks and the StoryMap

The HISTORYMUS team conducted 12 borderwalks during the period September-October 2024. Five of the borderwalks were with youth (3 in Bulgaria, 2 in Greek) and six with Bulgarian seniors. One of the borderwalks on the Bulgarian side consist of mix of youth and seniors. Altogether 27 people participated in the borderwalk research activity, of which 13 were young people and 14 seniors. Gender balance was carefully considered as 14 of the participants were women and 13 men (assumed). All conducted borderwalks followed the go-along method, except for one.³ In general, the borderwalk groups selected both cultural and natural sites whereas the historical sites, religious places and buildings, and the effect of the communist era were emphasized.

Borderwalk Group 1 and 2 took place in the city of Ivaylovgrad (BG), one of the largest cities in the eastern part of the Bulgarian-Greek border, and very close to the Bulgarian-Turkish border. Although groups did not cross the border during the walks, participants told stories about their experiences of crossing the border, primarily to Greek and occasionally to Turkey. Both groups shared stories of how their relatives had gone to Greek in search of work. Borderwalk GROUPS 3 and 4 took place in Thessaloniki (GR) with Greek youth. Thessaloniki is Greek's second-largest city, located in the northern part of the country, close to Bulgaria, the Republic of North Macedonia, and Turkey. Both borderwalks took place in the urban landscape of the historical center of Thessaloniki.

The borderwalk Groups 5-12 took place in villages near the Bulgaria-Greek border, within the eastern part of Blagoevgrad province (BG), specifically in the municipalities of Garmen, Hadzhidimovo, and Satovcha. The villages in which border walks were conducted were: Garmen 1 group, Ilinden 2 groups, Dabnitsa 2 group, Slashten 2 groups, Satovcha 1 group. These villages lie in the Mesta River valley, nestled between the Pirin and West Rhodope Mountains, and near the Greek border. This region is known for its significant Muslim population, including Bulgarians, Roma, and Turks, all of whom primarily speak Bulgarian, though some, particularly the Roma and Turks, also speak Turkish as their first language.

The borderwalks were conducted either in Bulgarian or in English. Bulgarian was the native language of researchers and all participants in groups 1-2, 5-12, which made borderwalks easy to carry out. Thus, different dialects and some Islamic terms which the researchers were not familiar with, posed some minor challenges for understanding. GROUPS 3 and 4 were carried out in English which was a second language for all participants and the HISTORYMUS team. The lack of a common first language did not feel as a barrier, because the participants and team members have a sufficient level of knowledge of English language.

³ A senior participant who was very involved in the village administration. Due to his age, he was not able to walk us through the village. The HISTORYMUS team thought that nevertheless this obstacle, the possibility of interviewing him should not be missed and they decided to conduct a standard indoor interview. After the end of the interview, they asked him to make a list of the places he was talking about and then the team made a walk through the village by themselves and took photos of the places that the participant had mentioned.

Moreover, one the team members has as well some knowledge of Greek, which occurred helpful when some clarifications were needed.

Table 8. The borderwalk groups conducted at the Bulgarian-Greek border region.

Borderwalk group code	Target group	Starting location/ country	No.umber of participants	Gender F/M (assumed)	Mobility	Date
Group1	Youth	Ivaylovgrad/BG	3	2/1	Walking/car	29.9.24
Group2	Senior	Ivaylovgrad/BG	3	2/1	Walking	29.9.24
Group3	Youth	Thessaloniki/GR	3	3/0	"	13.10.24
Group4	Youth	Thessaloniki/GR	3	1/2	"	14.10.24
Group5	Senior	Garmen/BG	1	0/1	"	29.10.24
Group6	Youth	Ribnovo/BG	2	1/1	"	29.10.24
Group7	Senior	Ilinden/BG	1	0/1	"	29.10.24
Group8	Senior	Ilinden/BG	3	0/3	"	29.10.24
Group9	Mixed	Dabnitsa/BG	3	2/1	"	30.10.24
Group10	Senior	Slashten/BG	1	0/1	"	30.10.24
Group11	Youth	Slashten/BG	2	2/0	"	30.10.24
Group12	Senior	Satovcha/BG	2	1/1	"	30.10.24

Table 9. The selected sites for the StoryMap from the Bulgarian-Greek borderland. The selection was based on researchers' selection.

At the Bulgarian side	At the Greek side	At the BG-GR border
The Center of Satovcha with willow tree	The town square in Slashten	Jewish Museum of Thessaloniki
The Church of Satovcha	The Christian Orthodox church in Dabnitsa	The tracks of the old trams
The Mosque of Satovcha,	<i>the new Muslim Cemetery</i>	The Byzantium building
The monument of Osten Uden	<i>the House of horrors</i>	Mustafa Kemal's house
Monument for soldiers	The main square of Dabnitsa	A roofed marketplace
The mosque of Dabnitsa	Church "St. Archangel Michael"	An Ottoman Mosque
The village park	School in Dabnitsa	
Streets of Dabnitsa	Beehives	
The city square in Ivaylovgrad	The city park	
Abandoned house	The old military unit	
the Greek neighborhood	The view towards Ivaylovgrad	
Planted pine trees	Refugees in Ivaylovgrad	

Figure 13. Screenshots illustrating the final digitalized BG-GR StoryMap.

Results

People's relations to landscapes: narratives and affects including dimensions of past, present and future

The borderwalk interview material from the four case border regions shows that participants considered the surrounding border landscape and its cross-border elements as valuable and meaningful. The meaningfulness became manifested through landscape narratives related to the dimensions of past, present and future. In the narratives, the historical stories, personal memories, everyday life at the border as well as future hopes for sustaining and preserving the natural and cultural landscape are intertwined, illustrating the importance and complex meaning of borders as people's heritage.

The past was present in the narratives both through participants' personal childhood memories and through wider public and historical narratives. Childhood and youthful memories were linked in many ways to everyday life at the border area whereas the historical stories concerned many times war history or contradictory time periods, such as socialistic era in Bulgaria. It was typical that the places and sites selected by the participants were assigned with both personal and local and national and historical meanings. It was common that participants introduced a site and a place through its historical narrative and then continued by telling how they have personal memories related to it as well. The personal memories strengthened the attachments to the places, and this became manifested especially in the borderwalks with seniors. The participants shared their unique experiences and social relations that are formed by and characteristics of living in a borderland. These include stories on border guards and how kids used to play border guards, for example.

The geohistories of the four border regions in question vary. Each border region offers a context through which the stories told by participants need to be interpreted and read through. Many significant memories and stories that stand out from the borderwalk material relate to the conflictual history of the border regions and how this history has influenced the lives of people and families in the border region over generations. The stories are related to official narratives about the region and its landscape and heritage, yet they are also all somehow related to the almost universal question of how it feels to belong and live in a borderland. In all border regions in Europe, war history and different border politics are present, yet perspectives may vary depending on the border. For others, the border area represented as a common meeting place even during the times of war and conflict whereas for others the enemy was just on the other side of the border.

The border landscapes narratives collected through the borderwalks differ between the border regions and also depending on the site and place of the research activity. Most borderwalks were conducted at land borders and border villages by foot. The borderwalks conducted at the Swedish-Danish maritime border region took place mostly on and in the vicinity of a ferry, however. Thus, the stories about the past were largely related to memories of everyday life at the border region, ferry journeys, family outings, and shopping trips, and less about the historical conflicts that were key themes in the other three case regions. At the southern European border region, Bulgarian-Greek border, participants recalled particularly life during socialist era, with strict border controls and police supervision. This era is remembered as a problematic regional heritage as people had to justify and give reasons for their presence at the border. Wartime and conflicts are also common themes in the public narratives of the four borderlands. In Thessaloniki, the narratives told by the youth show some nostalgia towards the glory of the medieval Greek

empire. The historical coexistence and interaction of different cultural and ethnic groups was seen as an important part of the landscape and identity of the city.

The present day was present in the narratives through everyday practices. The stories told by participants about the border landscape were many times linked to places which are important for them – where they go, and where they spend time; beaches, grocery stores, ferries, restaurants, pedestrian ways, market squares, sport stadium and other mundane places. The participants' everyday life appears to be characterized in many ways by open borders and border crossings. This was case especially at the northern European borderlands but in lesser extent in Bulgarian-Greek border which was still not part of Schengen at the time of our research activities. Bulgaria joined to Schengen area in January 2025. Although maintaining free movement across borders and removing border controls were seen as of high importance, the role of European Union and European integration was absent from the discussions both at the Danish-German and Finnish-Swedish border regions. The European Union appeared as absent also at the Danish-Swedish border, although it is worth noting that it was something that Swedish pensioners could see as problematic when they compared Sweden's integration with Europe rather than Denmark, as the latter connection is already well-established and natural. The elderly did not consider their relations relationship with Denmark problematic, as that connection is already well-established and natural, but Europe was perceived as remote and bureaucratic but essential. In Thessaloniki, the present-day narratives also concerned infrastructural and transportation challenges of the city. The disappearance of old tram tracks and the long-delayed metro project point to a city grappling with modernization while trying to retain its historical essence. Some participants said that the roofed Ottoman-era marketplace, though still in use, remains underappreciated. According to the participants, the upcoming metro station in the vicinity of the marketplace means that the place may gain new relevance.

For the future, it was generally considered important that the border landscape remains open, and border crossing is facilitated. Despite the challenges pointed out by the Swedish seniors, the view on the EU remains positive, emphasizing the benefits of living close to Europe and maintaining good relations across the border. The interviews at the Bulgarian-Greek border also show an undercurrent of optimism towards European integration, driven by EU-funded initiatives aimed at improving infrastructure, education, and cultural heritage of the borderland. The narratives of minorities and migrants were also present. At the Bulgarian-Greek border, migrants crossing the Bulgarian border create fear and uncertainty, especially among senior residents who perceive them as unfamiliar and not belonging in their borderland landscape. Thus, the way the future was discussed during the borderwalks, was many times linked to the present day, for example how contemporary matters, such as open borders, should be sustained for future generations as well. The future mostly had to do with normative visions of how things 'out to be' in the border region. The border regions are different in many ways and their landscape narratives need to be considered contextually.

The study of the **Danish-German** border pointed out many significant memories and stories relate to the conflictual history of the border region, that is also an important part of the public heritage narratives. History has influenced families in the border region over generations, forming specific minority affiliations. Many stories also related to border guarding and "border games" as people's heritage:

Since we were children, we played in the area from here and then to Bov. We were always aware of what was on the other side of the water. That we did not go there. And if there were any German customs officers or border guards, we usually hid ourselves... The thing about defectors was in all of us. When we played something, it was often that we had to help

the police, or we had to help the border guards because a defector had been seen and they couldn't find him. (Seniors, DK, Group 2)

In the Danish-German borderland, there is also a significant difference between the memories of borderlanders living on the East coast and those living on the West coast. On the West coast, the sea and water are often an integral part of the stories and memories, and the sites participants spoke about the historical importance of the sea. The sea does not have the same importance or significance in the Eastern part of the region, where the sites chosen were often official memorials with a connected narrative. The water, in this case the Baltic Sea and Flensborg Fjord was not mentioned very often. One 'borderwalk' (with GROUP 3) was therefore deliberately conducted as a boat trip on the fjord, yet here the stories were not related to the presence of the sea but to experiences of shopping and social engagements on the boat itself. Crossing the border with a boat is an important part of people's lived landscape and heritage.

The present-day borderings were not as significant in the material collected as were narratives related to past histories and experiences. Most of the present-day narratives related to the interlocutors' everyday practice. Similarly, experiences of cross-border travel and shopping are an important part of peoples heritage and their often entwine with stories related to border games where one needs to know how to conduct oneself and behave at the border:

I know some young men who were stopped at the border and their whole car was searched. We therefore think about who sits where in the car. It should not be two men in the front, but a man/woman in front and at the back of the car. (Youth, DK, group 4)

Many stories underline how existence of the state border is arbitrary in a world where regulations are fundamentally the same in the entire territory covered by European Union member states. This relates to the existence of the single market and the Schengen agreement, including political discourses of the importance of open borders in Europe.

At the **Swedish-Danish** border, the historical significance of the border was vividly described through participants' recollections, highlighting the evolving meanings of cross-border interactions over different periods and life stages. The ferry journeys can be understood in terms of people's border heritage and for many there formed a specific site of transgenerational memory. Stories of ferry journeys, family outings, and shopping trips bring to life the ways the border is not only a physical line but also a cultural and social connector. When the border is discussed in a historical context, participants recalled their experiences, highlighting how cross-border interactions evolved over time. The tradition of touring (Tura) recurs in the participants' stories and is something that is said to be something that does not need explanation. To "tour" is self-evident as going back and forth across the border and enjoying the ferry offers without intention to get off on the other side or a destination point there. The Swedish pensioners who participated in the borderwalk, or border cruising, research activity, described it as "almost a must" in their younger years. They reminisced about going back and forth on the ferry, often making trips on Fridays and Saturdays before heading out for the evening. Over time, these trips became a weekly routine. One participant remarked that after starting a family, Saturdays were often spent ferrying across the strait to shop, filling their homes with goods purchased in Denmark. For many, the ferries themselves were memorable, serving as a unique cultural experience and a cornerstone of cross-border life.

Yes, it was almost a must when you were younger. You took turns, went back and forth. Then it was a trip on Fridays and Saturdays before going out... Then, when I had a family, you

would often go over on Saturday to shop. Yes, you filled the house and took the opportunity to grab something quickly there too. (Senior, SE, Group 1)

Festivals were also taken up as people's heritage. Some Danish pensioners also spoke about past cultural collaborations between the two cities, such as the Street Festival. They remembered how this event brought people together – both locally and from Sweden encouraging a sense of unity and connection between the communities. They said that such collaborations have decreased over time, lamenting that these shared cultural experiences were beneficial for both cities but are now less frequent, thus reflecting the change of the border landscape as a meeting place

In Knäred, which stand as a relict border landscape in southern Sweden, the seniors participating in the research activity reflected on their own connection to the border, recalling stories of everyday life shaped by its presence. From maintaining small farms near the boundary to navigating a landscape rich with historic markers and folklore, their experiences highlight how the border influenced daily routines and fostered a unique sense of place. 400 years after the border revisions between Sweden and Denmark, there is still a sense of the old border having some sort of impact. For them, such small farms formed a specific border heritage element in the landscape.

Comparison of the narratives from Knäred with other narratives talked about the Swedish-Danish border landscape highlight how the border's legacy is experienced differently in rural areas compared to the more urbanized Öresund region. While ferry trips and shopping dominate in coastal cities like Helsingborg and Helsingør, in Knäred, the border is reflected in quiet, preserved landscapes and everyday connections with its history. These present-day experiences in Knäred reveal how rural borderlands can offer a slower, more reflective engagement with border landscape heritage compared to the faster-paced urban border exchanges of the Öresund region. This balance of past and present provides a complementary perspective on how borders are lived and remembered across the region.

The future narratives often focus on increased contacts and ease of mobility, even as the broader relationship between Sweden, Denmark and the EU continue to evolve.

Participant 2: I don't think much about the EU in the future.

Participant 5: No, it's just a place we hear about. We travel to France and Italy, but it feels far away.

Participant 1: It seems very abstract.

Participant 6: Yes, we talk more about Danish politics and less about the EU.

Participant 4: Exactly.

Participant 2: The EU feels like something distant, without much influence.

Participant 3: We focus on the immediate, what matters most to us.

Participant 2: Yes, the EU is too big and bureaucratic.

Participant 6: Gradually it's difficult to get involved in it.

Participant 2: Exactly, the interest is just not there.

Participant 4: It all seems far away, and you don't feel like you have any influence.

(Seniors, DK, Group 4)

Contrary to the border between Helsingør and Helsingborg, in the old border of Knäred, the future of the border is seen through a focus on preservation and sustainable engagement with its history as a “double” border (national and administrative between counties). Efforts to maintain walking trails, restore historic markers, and celebrate local dialects reflect a desire to keep the border’s heritage alive for future generations. Participants expressed hope that Knäred could serve as a cultural and ecological hub, complementing the urban-centric dynamics of the Öresund region.

The research activities at the **Finnish-Swedish** border region took place in Tornio-Haparanda twin city. Two focus groups were conducted in more rural and natural environment with local people who participated traditional net fishing (*kulkustaminen*) at Pekanpää and Vittangi villages at the Tornio River. The two sets of interview material differ and inform us about different aspects of border landscape as people’s heritage. Past was present in the narratives both through participants’ personal memories from childhood and through historical narratives. While childhood and youthful memories were linked in many ways everyday living at the border area, the historical stories were mostly related to war history which had taken place at the region – memorials and historical sites such as railway bridge between Tornio (FI) and Haparanda (SE) and military bunkers in Haparanda. For Pekanpää and Vittangi villages, the historical stories were related more on the border river and regulations related to local fishing – starting from time when Finland was under the Swedish rule.

Meaningful places often related to war history such as railway bridge, railway station, military bunkers, Haparanda beach/embankment, Haparanda’s city hotel but some of them dated back further in the past, such as the tar depot (Tjärhov). It was common that participants introduced places through its historical narrative and then continued how they have personal memories related to it as well. Also, current geopolitical tensions and migration were discussed as there are many sites commemorating evacuees and other war memories in the border landscape. Seniors and youth also attached similar meanings to certain places. The old military bunkers built in WWI at the Swedish end of railway bridge between Sweden and Finland/Russia offer a fitting example. In these conversations the historical meaning, personal memories, and places’ present increased importance due to geopolitical threats, being Russia, were intertwined.

As part of the wider landscape, the cities of Tornio and Haparanda in themselves were seen as important places and nodes of local interaction but also as national and international meetings places. Many stories related to the public narrative of the wars that are commemorated in the landscape in many ways. An important site for many, for young and seniors, was the War Child Memorial commemorating the 80 000 Finnish children who were placed in Sweden during WWII. The monument evoked emotional narratives of children and their experiences in times of war:

It shows the children who have come to Sweden, kept safe when there was war. [...] It is important to remember. (Youth, SE, Group 5)

Some stories related to old times and places that no longer existed in the material landscape, the old customs (*tullikoppi*) for example, formed one important site in senior people’s memorization of the border landscape. Similarly, the border fences during the COVID-19 border closure were still part of the landscape in the mind of many people. The landscape transitions influence how the participants see and narrate the change in the extent and dynamics in the interaction across borders. The border closure due to COVID-19 pandemic was seen as a drastic event for both young and senior people living in the area. Thus, it made visible the integrated nature of the border cities and even for those participants who did not necessarily have so many contacts across the borders at the time, the border closure deprived the “self-evident” *possibilities* for border crossings. Covidfencing initiated the division between people living in Tornio and Haparanda, and increased mistrust. Such polarization between local people was seen as a future threat.

The passenger traffic connections across the border were considered important. The railway connection between Tornio and Haparanda is now being electrified by national infrastructure and transportation agencies which enable passenger traffic. This was seen as important by both seniors and youth and would make public transportation more efficient and facilitative connections and security in the future. Future concerns also included the plans for extensive wind farm in Tornio. The participants saw the windmills as a threat which would harm, or even destroy, the border landscape.

In the **Bulgarian-Greek** border people remember the border through historical events and practices that shaped the border region. Participants frequently recalled life during the socialist era, with strict border controls and police supervision.

Back in the socialist era, there was a border fence – exactly where people used to go to the river. A large wire fence was in the middle, guarded by soldiers who did not allow crossing. There used to be control at the entrance to the village. People were stopped when they went for firewood, and their donkeys were checked because there were no carts. It was difficult to get permission to cross. (Youth, BG, Youth 11).

Participants showed historical landmarks, religious sites, and places related to late-communist history. A notable common thread across the interviews was the significance of schools and reading halls ("читалище"), which were central cultural and educational hubs during the communist era. These buildings, which often housed libraries, theaters, and folk groups, were frequently mentioned as important spaces for social and cultural life. In Ribново, one participant even detailed the history of secular education in the village, which was particularly fascinating. Many of the participants also shared personal stories about mosques in the region, reflecting the religious diversity in the villages, especially in places like Ribново, Dabnitsa, and Slashten. Participants, particularly the older ones, recounted their experiences of the "Revival process", a state-enforced assimilation campaign that sought to forcibly alter the names and cultural practices of the Muslim population in the late 1980s.

Younger participants also mentioned the Revival process, but they did so in more distant terms, viewing it as part of history rather than a lived experience. Additionally, continued links with ethnically Turkish Bulgarian citizens expelled during the "Revival Process"⁴ and their contributions to local infrastructure, like the renovated hospital in Momchilgrad, connects the region's past to its present.

I chose to give birth to my child at the hospital in Momchilgrad (BG). It's really nice there because it was completely renovated. Everything was done and donated by Turks—Turks who were expelled from Bulgaria at the end of the communist regime during the so-called "Revival Process." These people now live in Turkey, but they still have relatives here and return from time to time. (Youth, BG, Group 1)

Today, the border is an integral part of the everyday landscape of people living in the borderlands. The landscape is also shaped by cross-border interactions, such as Greeks shopping in Bulgaria and visiting Bulgarian hospitals, reflecting mutual dependencies. The border also influences local traditions, with beekeeping near the border being a cherished environmental connection. Participants of the borderwalk

⁴ The "Revival Process" was a government-led campaign in Bulgaria during the 1980s aimed at forcibly assimilating the Turkish minority by changing their names to Bulgarian ones, restricting their cultural practices, and encouraging their migration from the country.

research activity at the Bulgarian-Greek border expressed both concerns and hopes for the future. Some were concerned about the settlement of refugees through European projects and highlighted fears over socio-economic imbalance and resource strain. There is also an undercurrent of optimism for the future. One participant notes that the investment in schools and housing in some towns is a sign of potential revitalization and future growth.

Different age groups perceptions of borders' impact on landscapes

The second objective of the border landscapes as heritage research is to study how different age groups (youth, seniors) relate to borders' impact on landscapes (O5.2).

In the **Danish-German** border, alike in the other case regions, one significant difference between the generations and their way of telling stories concerns temporalities. The seniors were much more focused on the past than the younger generation. This concerns both official historical narratives and their own personal memories. The conversations with the senior generation often circled around their childhood and youth experiences, as well as around the more "non-personal" historical narratives of the region.⁵ Such narratives can be understood to communicate specific knowledge of the border and the border landscape as people's heritage. The younger generation told significantly more stories about present-day experiences with borders.

The border doesn't mean much to us. At least we don't pay much attention to it, even though we spend a lot of our time on both sides of the border. We often visit friends and family in Denmark. Maybe the border doesn't matter so much because we feel like we belong on both sides of it. (Youth, DE, Group 10)

This difference between present-day and past experiences also relates to a difference between youth and seniors in terms of how they narrate their stories. Youth tell stories more by using short sentences and headlines, and by using less narrative structure, like plot, build up and culmination. This might be related to how the youth are used to communicating using social media platforms where messages are usually brief and precise. On their side, the older generation we engaged with what could be called "rehearsed narrative", that is, stories they had obviously told many times before to several others. These narratives would also follow more usual narrative structure, like the one mentioned above – plot/build-up/culmination – or they would be snap-shots of official historical accounts, often also 'the grand narrative', about the region's conflict-ridden history.

There was a significant difference between the younger and older generations in the ways they articulate the importance of national context. The seniors were more 'national' in their narratives, yet also recognizing the importance of interaction with 'the other side'. Their stories are significantly about national difference, as in the Danes doing this, and the Germans doing this, here illustrated by the difference in how the two nationalities would traditionally build their houses:

There is a German and a Danish house next to each other. Once you open your eyes to it, you can easily see which is Danish and which is German style buildings. Well, it is the building

⁵ The seniors often told stories in similar ways as was the case in history books, educational material and tourism brochures (Internal report 2023).

style that is characteristic. A Danish craftsman at that time would not think of building a house in that way. (Seniors, DK, Group 2)

The younger generation seem to be more focused on border-crossing in their narratives (not all though), without any obvious need to indicate if one is either Dane or German (or something other) in their narratives. Many younger generation participants were themselves in several ways border-crossers; many had lived in either country, and many went to the minority institutions' schools and often mastered both languages.

The national context plays an important role also in the **Swedish-Danish** border region where the most striking differences in the narratives were not found between age groups but between nationalities. The Swedish pensioners emphasize touring —the tradition of ferrying back and forth for leisure, dining, and socializing to a much greater extent than their Danish counterparts, who instead highlight the trips to shop and visit what they consider to be a country that is exotic (Sweden). This distinction underscores the varying ways the border has been integrated into the cultural and social lives of the two nations, shaped by their unique perspectives and historical experiences. Taking ferry with the Swedish pensioner and youth groups allowed to gain understanding of a water borders in the landscape and the experience of crossing the border.

For young people today, the border is not something they actively think about, but it has become a completely natural part of life even when they do not actually cross that often or have more difficulties than the older generation understanding the language of the other. For the young Swedish group, the physical state boundary was more abstract as crossing it was done either via the bridge between Copenhagen and Malmö or via the ferry connection. The older people talked a lot about what it was like in the past and went all the way back to their own childhood. Taking the ferry meant, among other things, that you went over travelled to Denmark/Sweden to shop. Back then, it was for things that were either cheaper or wasn't accessible at home. Additional themes discussed were memories from "touring". These were especially referenced when they were young and partied on the ferry. Many senior participants recall ferry trips as a central social activity, offering both practical benefits, such as access to cheaper goods, and opportunities for community bonding. However, some Swedes expressed concerns about rising costs for ferry trips, not so much the cost of the ferry itself but for the prices on the Danish side.

Both Swedish and Danish pensioners tell similar stories about these cross-border experiences, though some differences stood out. Danish participants often expressed amazement at the quantity of goods available in Sweden after the war. In contrast, Swedish pensioners tended to focus on the ease with which alcohol could be purchased in Denmark, reflecting the differing priorities and cultural practices of the time.

Back then there were also many restrictions after the war. On plastic products, for example. I remember the booze boats that sailed between Copenhagen and Sweden. They handed out free tickets to get people on board and buy goods on the ships... It was a private enterprise, so it was about making money, and it was cheap to come to Sweden back then... It was exotic to go ashore in Sweden. I was maybe 10 years old the first time we did it. I remember almonds and all the special things you could buy. (Seniors, DK, Group 1).

The seniors expressed a strong sense of nostalgia when discussing about the past – particularly their youth's experiences of the border area were often told in a romantic shimmer; the feeling that it was a different time than with different conditions than today is clear. For them, the border area once represented a space of adventure and novelty, shaped by the unique cultural and economic exchanges of

that time. They highlighted the different motives for crossing the border that existed then in relation to those that apply to them today. When border controls were introduced due to migration controls and COVID-19, they were perceived as unnatural and troublesome. At the same time, it was discussed by both the Swedish and Danish pensioners' groups that it is problematic with too much free access for people who do not have citizenship.

The transformation of the Öresund landscape into a meeting place has had varied effects on different demographic groups. While many benefit from the region's fluid borders and shared spaces, certain groups experience these dynamics differently. For younger residents, the Öresund region offers a sense of freedom and opportunity. Many youths describe the ease of movement across the strait as a normal part of life, with trips to Denmark or Sweden feeling akin to local travel. Some interviewees mentioned that they see Helsingør as an extension of Helsingborg or even as a neighbourhood rather than a separate country, independent of our frequent or rare these trips are in reality.

In December, me and another girl in the class went over to Helsingør with some boys. We sat down at a café there and then we went home again. (Youth, SE, Group 1)

When I go to Malmö, it feels very smooth. I can just get on the train and check in with the same travel card I use in Denmark. Even Malmö station has Danish 'check-in' machines... Sometimes Malmö almost feels like an extension of Copenhagen. (Youth, DK, Group 1)

Notably, for older residents, the Öresund landscape is often associated with memories of a more defined border and the traditions tied to it. For youth the physical border has been less visible, yet their narratives also note the subtle ways in which borders still influence identity. For example, a young Swedish participant residing in Denmark highlighted being labeled as “the Swede” in class when speaking Swedish.

In the context of the **Finnish-Swedish** border, the participants' everyday life appears to be in many ways characterized by open borders and their cross-border dimensions. The tradition related to cross-border cooperation between these cities was seen as meaningful in the landscape in the present. These places such as common Victoria's square and the travel center were seen to have strong symbolic value. Moreover, the free movement across borders was strongly emphasized at “border sites” such as Victoria's Square in Tornio-Haparanda, bridges, Tornio River. Maintaining free movement across borders also in the future was seen as of high importance. Especially youth underlined the importance sustaining places were both Finns and Sweds can meet and gather. Some participants narrated Tornio-Haparanda twin city as a unique space which is simultaneously the same and different.

I like it because it's really a strange feeling. Now you just go ten minutes and then you are kind of foreigner. And at the same time, it's my home. I mean, when we're talking about having a lunch, we don't talk about having lunch in Haparanda or Tornio, we're talking about places like Golden Flower [Chinese restaurant in Tornio] or something in that way. (Seniors, SE, Group 10)

Tornio River forms an important landscape element. The participants considered it as a fundamental part of the border landscape, a site of various historical and everyday events and stories. The border river was considered, among others, as a historical passage between Europe and the Arctic Ocean, a source of livelihood and food, and a place for different leisure activities. The value of the long, free-flowing river itself was emphasized in participants' narratives. “One of the Europe's longest free rivers” (Senior/FIN/GROUP8). For youth, the meaning of the river was more linked to its general role as a part of the border landscape and as a site for different leisure activities such as swimming, boating, (ice)fishing and driving snowmobiles, while in the seniors' narratives, the meaning of border river in the landscape was more multidimensional

and especially the river's seasonal characteristics and its importance in local peoples' lived heritage and memories.

An important finding regarding the Finnish-Swedish border region is that, when using the go-along method, youth and senior groups selected many similar sites and places. Popular places for both groups included Victoria's square, Haparanda Stadshotell, Haparanda beach/embankment, Museum of Tornio Valley, War Child memorial, Mia Green's memorial and Hermansons. These places can be considered as part of the institutional border landscape narrative, and they are also important for local people's sense of place. The historical places and monuments are part of the lived border landscape and speaking about the history of the border regions, the experiences of war children for example, can be an emotional experience. Youth had also selected sites which were not directly related to border or border history such as Pikisaari beach, water towers, and sport stadium. Such like in the other border regions, also in the Finnish-Swedish borderland the seniors' narratives of border landscape as heritage were many times "richer" in terms of length and details whereas youths' stories were shorter and conversational.

The borderwalks at the **Bulgarian-Greek** border showed that both youth and senior participants value the landscape but have different perspectives based on their generational experiences. Seniors recall the controlled and secure environment of the socialist era, where the border was a rigid boundary. They focus on the past as a time when the border offered stability and economic security. The seniors also emphasize traditional practices and the old social structure that once existed. The younger generation values the landscape for its environmental aspects, such as the freedom they feel when spending time in nature. They also see the border as an evolving and more open space, reflecting modern-day mobility and opportunities for interaction across borders. Youth tend to highlight natural spaces like forests, beehives, and other environmental spots. These places are seen as spaces for recreation, environmental engagement, and personal connection.

We studied at universities in other cities in the country, but we couldn't adapt there because we're used to nature. We really miss that. We miss the environment. [...]. It's literally... it's freedom. When I go with my friend to the beehives in the forest, I literally feel afterward as if they've put me on a fast recharge. (Youth, BG, Group1).

Seniors focus more on urban and historical places, such as old factories, border checkpoints, and areas shaped by migration or historical events. These places have a stronger socio-political significance and reflect memories of the socialist era and past economic life. Senior participants emphasize the structured, economically stable environment of the socialist era, where the border was a tool of control. Youth acknowledge the past but with less emotional connection, viewing it through the lens of change and transformation. Youth see the border landscape as a place for exploration and environmental engagement, with more fluid and open interactions across borders. Moreover, as Greek youth underlines in the context of Turkish youth studying in Thessaloniki, state borders and possible border obstacles are understood somewhat instrumentally, something which just needs to be crossed.

I know that now more and more Turkish people are coming to Thessaloniki to study and these are not only Turkish youngsters from the neighboring regions. They come here to study because on that way they can acquire European degree. They say that for them crossing the border is not a big issue – it is a necessary achievable obstacle although there is a border control police from both sides of the border and in the weekend and holidays there may be a big queue on the border check. I personally know such people. (Youth, GR, Group 3)

The seniors, on the other hand, are concerned with the current issues of migration and fear the neglect of their towns due to social changes. For the future, youth express optimism, focusing on the potential for regional development, modernization, and the sustainable use of resources. The seniors show skepticism, particularly regarding European projects and the sustainability of small communities, with fears of cultural and economic erosion. Youth narratives focus on personal connections to nature and the freedom they experience in the environment, as well as the excitement of modern life in an interconnected world. Seniors tend to narrate through personal anecdotes that reflect socio-political changes, focusing on the importance of maintaining cultural identity and remembering the structured past.

In Thessaloniki, the walks with young citizens provided an insight into the historical and cultural complexity of the city's landscape, best understood as a palimpsest landscape where various cultural and historical borders criss-cross. The citizens participating in the borderwalk research activity highlighted the importance of the city's historical heritage, not only as a reminder of the past but also as an active part of the modern city identity. During the walks in Ladadika in Thessaloniki it came out that youth value its transformation into a vibrant nightlife center; the participants expressed a wish that the whole city could undergo similar revitalization. They also note that historical sites, such as a Byzantine building under renovation, often go unnoticed by locals. The discussion of borders during the walking activity also extended beyond the places and sites visited. In youth mentioned the growing number of Turkish students coming to the city for education, viewing the border as a bureaucratic hurdle rather than a significant barrier. This movement of people continues the historical exchange between Thessaloniki and Turkey, reinforced by shared cultural and historical ties, such as the house where Mustafa Kemal Atatürk was born in 1881 is now part of the Turkish Consulate.

Common nature and landscape bring people together across borders

The third research objective for border landscapes as heritage research was to study how common nature and landscape can bring people together across borders (O5.3). In the **Danish-German** border region many narratives included notions of different activities such as sledge-riding in the winter, attending festivals in the countryside, hiking (see examples above); as well as ferry rides, including stories of shopping and smuggling: or simply just 'looking towards the other side'. These stories highlight bringing people together across borders, or, maybe better, they are bringing people from either side of the border (and internationally) in contact with each other. In this sense the landscape appears to have a relational and even integrating function to play. There was also one story about a more political happening, which brought people from both sides of the border together in a more physical sense, namely the volleyball match between members of both minorities using the Wild Boar Fence as a net. The nature of the borderland does not appear as an independent factor in the stories, and it is very similar on either side of the border. Rather, the natural and cultural heritage are related to the Eastern and Western parts of the border region being very different in terms of landscape, for example the water and the landscape overall is more present in the stories told about the Eastern part. In this sense the state border has had a significant impact on the way local people relate to the borderlands in which they live, no longer recognizing the way the landscape integrates the two countries because of its similarity across the border. The border crossing landscape seems to be much more present in the tourism material from the region (see above for more about this), when promoting hiking trips and bicycle rides along the border, trips that cross the border and make the participants notice the similarities of the landscape across the border.

The sites chosen and the narratives talked about describing the region and its borders, indicates that heritage is most often connected with "cultural heritage", that is, sites like monuments or museums, or

places used for leisure activities, and not that often with natural heritage and the natural landscapes of the borderlands. The location at the sea is mentioned in relation to these leisure and other economic activities, and on the West coast the young people do mention the marsh and the dikes by the water as places where they do things, yet mostly it is as if people do not see nature, rather people are in nature. Considering our focus in the research on landscape, the researcher also expected more discourses about the importance of preserving the environment and nature, especially in the Eastern context, yet these discourses were completely absent from the material.

The **Öresund region** is rich in local traditions and meeting places that have historically brought people together across borders, creating a shared cultural landscape. These traditions and spaces reflect the intertwined lives of Swedish and Danish residents and highlight the role of physical and cultural landmarks in fostering cross-border connections. The ferry itself can be understood as an important bridge in the region. The ferries are more than just transportation—they serve as “floating” restaurants and communal spaces where locals gather. Many participants described Tura as a central part of their lives, whether it was a weekly routine to shop for goods like butter and wine or an occasion to celebrate family milestones. The tradition extends across generations, with older residents recalling subsidized group trips organized by pensioner associations and younger participants noting the casual ease of hopping on a ferry with friends. For many, “touring” exemplifies how the Öresund strait continues to act as a connector rather than a divider, allowing residents to share experiences that transcend national boundaries. The bridge between Copenhagen and Malmö enhanced this connector aspect, as well as a fixed link between Helsingborg and Helsingør would, by making car and train rides easier while also embodying a loss of something valuable (the Tura tradition).

Another bridging element were the Collaborative Festivals and historical meeting places, the Gadefestival is a street festival, organized as a joint effort between Helsingborg and Helsingør, and it brings together residents from both sides of the strait through music, food, and cultural displays. Participants remember the festival as a vibrant symbol of cross-border collaboration, fostering friendships and a sense of shared identity. Although such initiatives have become less frequent, they remain a testament to the potential of cultural events to unite communities across borders, forming an important people’s heritage.

There have been some interesting collaborations, especially in the past... for example the Street Festival, which started about 10 years ago. It was a joint project between the cities. I remember how it brought people together – both locally and from Sweden. But it seems like there is less collaboration now than before. It's strange, because it was good for both cities.
(Seniors, DK, Group 1)

The region's historic landmarks also serve as significant meeting places for the borderlanders. Kronborg Castle, famously linked to Shakespeare’s Hamlet, is a site of cultural and historical importance that attracts visitors from both Sweden and Denmark. Beyond its historical significance, the castle symbolizes the shared heritage of the region, offering a space where people from both sides can connect and reflect on their common past. Ferry terminals are another key example of functional meeting points that double as social spaces. Whether it is a casual stop for coffee, shopping, or simply watching the activity of the strait, these terminals are integral to the daily lives of Öresund residents. They provide an accessible and neutral ground where the lines between Swedish and Danish identities blur, emphasizing shared cultural and economic practices.

In Knäred, common heritage is deeply tied to its traditions and preserved meeting places that connect the past with the present. The walking trails and restored border markers serve not only as physical reminders of the old Swedish-Danish border. Folklore, such as the stories of "Danska backen" and gatherings at

historic landmarks, enriches the cultural memory of the area. These traditions, coupled with efforts to protect natural landscapes, highlight Knäred's role as a quieter but equally significant contributor to the region's shared heritage, offering a complementary perspective to the bustling urban dynamics of the Öresund region.

As discussed in the above section, the Öresund region exemplifies how landscapes can serve as meeting places that foster connections across borders. Over time, the dynamics of rebordering and debordering have shaped how people engage with the region's natural and built environment. These spaces have transformed into unifying elements that connect border communities while preserving their shared heritage. The sense of an "invisible border" has significant implications for how the landscape functions as a meeting place. Clearly, the human-made Öresund bridge has become a part of the "natural" landscape, but at the same ferries at Helsingør-Helsingborg take up a similar position. At the same time, this is not something that was directly expressed by the participants in the borderwalks. The Öresund strait itself is a unifying natural feature, drawing residents from both sides to its shores. Beaches and waterfront promenades are popular meeting places, where people gather to enjoy the scenery, participate in water sports, or simply relax. The shared appreciation of the natural beauty of the strait could potentially reinforce the region's identity as a collective space. Likewise, trails and natural reserves in the Öresund region could provide spaces for exploration and connection. For example, the historic walking trail in Knäred could offer more residents and visitors a chance to engage with the region's past while enjoying its natural environment.

Knäred provides an additional perspective on how landscapes reflect the dynamics of rebordering and debordering. Unlike the invisible borders of the Öresund strait, Knäred's border remains tangible through its historic markers, preserved walking trails, and local folklore. Efforts to maintain trails and markers demonstrate how rural landscapes can preserve the memory of borders while serving as spaces for cross-cultural engagement and ecological stewardship, complementing the urban focus of the Öresund region. The borderwalk narratives in this border region focused on present and past experiences and memories whereas the future of the borderland and preserving the historical border was not taken up in the discussions. Yet, by leveraging its natural landscapes and historical significance, Knäred has the potential to remain a meaningful place, emphasizing sustainability, cultural preservation, and cross-border collaboration as regional and people's heritage.

In the **Finnish-Swedish** border region, there are several ways how the common heritage of nature and landscape have been and do bring people together across borders at this region. The Tornio River is seen as a fundamental element of the culture of Tornio Valley and which brings people together from both sides of the border.

Participant 1: I think the river is so important because [...] it makes us part of the Torne Valley. This river isn't just here, it's all the way up. So it's very important. And I mean, it's the Tornedalian culture and different things.

Participant 2: It's a big identity thing too for the people who live near the river. So it ties people together somehow (Seniors, SE, Group 10)

The traditional net fishing method *kulkustaminen* which is being practiced in only a few locations along the Tornio River illustrates as a good example. This traditional salmon and white fish fishing method is nowadays highly regulated by states and bringing local people together to the River every June (salmon) and August (white fish). Moreover, fishing rights are tied to land ownership which makes it very exclusive activity in the border landscape, highlighting that people's heritage can be also contested and exclusive.

The tradition therefore connects people across the border in a differentially inclusive manner. Interestingly, the Finnish seniors point out how the river's role as a state border has enabled the continuity of this traditional fishing – referring to argued looser policies on fishing quotas in Sweden.

At the Tornio River, there are so-called sovereignty islands, which were not divided when the border was drawn. This means there are islands owned by Finns on the Swedish side of the border and vice versa. These sovereignty islands were considered as common meeting places for both Finns and Swedes as on those islands, there are shared fishing/hunting sheds used by local people for instance, for grilling. From the more urban environment of Tornio-Haparanda there were different events mentioned by participants which have brought people together across the border. Firstly, the common New Year's celebration event at the common Victoria's square was seen as an important event by both youth and seniors. The different time zones of Finland and Sweden makes it possible to celebrate the change of new year twice. Also, the big ice fishing competition (*Tornion suurpilkit*) which are held at a central spot next to the Tornio old bridge at the Tornio River every winter was considered as an important event gathering people together, also further away.

In addition, valuing the shared border landscape can bring people together across the borders. This has happened in the case of wind farm plans which have caused strong opposition among local people, on both sides of the border. This illustrates how the shared resistance, in this case towards the city of Tornio as a land use planner and the windmill company, can initiate and embrace valuing the common border landscape as a meeting place.

One wind power company is planning to build wind power plant here [close by in] Karhakkamaa [in Finnish side] and it has brought people together. There has been very strong opposition. We have held many meetings and written various petitions together. Here in Swedish side these have been sent to Naturvårdsvärket. So it has created a lot of co-operation [across the borders]. (Seniors, SE, Group 12)

The border closure due to COVID-19 pandemics had a drastic effect of border landscape as a meeting place and increased the mistrust between local people. However, re-bordering processes can also take place indirectly and unconsciously as an effect of depopulating processes as described above. Broader discourses which were present in the borderwalk interview material were, among others, free movement, united Tornio valley and its counter discourse polarization, as well as geopolitical changes and threatening Russia. Interestingly, the European Union is completely absent from the stories told by participants.

The **Bulgarian-Greek** border landscape has shifted from a restrictive barrier to a more open region, facilitating cross-border interactions. The socialist era's border controls have given way to freer movement across borders, encouraging trade, shared services, and cultural exchanges. For example, Greeks visit Bulgaria for shopping, and locals cross borders to access better healthcare. Also, daily based commuting across the border have increased and Bulgarians go collecting cotton in the Greek fields, for instance. Thus, these debordering processes have enabled and created spaces for everyday interaction. Environmental activities, such as beekeeping, are also shared practices across the border, fostering a sense of common heritage in the landscape. EU funding is seen as a unifying force, promoting regional development, peace, and environmental protection. While some residents express distrust in these initiatives, believing they overshadow local needs, others see EU projects as vital for improving infrastructure and cultural heritage. Environmental protection and sustainability are also common concerns, with both countries working together on nature conservation and climate efforts. However, cross-border cooperation remains uneven in some areas due to local tensions.

Thus, it is interesting how re- and debordering processes shape natural landscape as well, and how the meaning of landscape elements can change over time. For instance, in Ivaylovgrad, the dams in the mountain area close to the Bulgarian-Greek-Turkish border area were originally built for military defense and represented potential threat but are now considered as meeting places for leisure activities.

We have very large dams above Ivaylovgrad. Some people even go fishing there. Recently, they built gazebos along the shore. All three reservoirs are part of the Arda River cascades. They were built for strategic purposes back in the day - in case of an attack from the Greeks or Turks, the power plants would be blown up, and the huge amount of water would flood the valley, drowning everything. Of course, it is unnecessary now. (Seniors, BG, Group 2)

Some participants were concerned about future development. Many participants express frustration with local governance issues such as corruption, nepotism, and unequal access to jobs and resources, which hinder the development of the border region. Environmental connection was important for both youth and senior residents as they deeply value nature, considering it an integral part of their heritage and identity. The landscape, including forests and other natural spaces, plays a central role in their understanding of community and place. These findings suggest that the border region, while offering future opportunities for connection, also presents significant challenges related to the concerns over migration, inequality, and environmental sustainability. To foster inclusiveness and mutual understanding of future development needs, these issues must be addressed and carefully contemplated.

Discussion

The research findings together with the digitalized Story Maps offer new understanding about border landscapes as heritage. To respond to the objectives of the research, we have analyzed the temporal and spatial dimensions of the border landscape narratives, how they are lived with and perceived by different generations of people and what agencies they bring forth. This has allowed us to provide new understanding of how borders shape perceptions of European landscapes and create dialogue between a place-based approach and identity-based theorizations of borders as heritage. The findings and stories discussed in this report need to be interpreted in relation to the research contexts and the participating citizen group. The four border regions formed unique contexts in terms of their geohistory and considering the process and phases of European integration. The border regions also varied from rural to urbanized border landscapes, the former perspective often focusing on the preservation of traditional ways of life and the latter with more cosmopolitan and international experiences with borders and border crossings. The two northernmost border regions are simultaneously divided and connected by a water border which powerfully shapes the citizens' perceptions of the landscape and highlights the importance of cross-border bridges and ferry routes as heritage.

The results offer understanding about the ways in which public narratives and discourses on borders are significant for citizens living in the European border regions and how local people make sense of the border landscape as heritage through public discourses, local narratives and their personal life experiences. The results show that the narratives and perceptions of border landscapes differ in all four border regions and between young and elderly citizens. Youth voices highlight a familiar relationship with the border landscape, for example, younger participants described often the practical crossings rather than cultural connectors. In comparison, the senior group narratives were often tied to shared meeting places and past social gatherings. The older generation often narrated themselves as closely connected with the border region as a place that has shaped who they are and what values they have. Related to this, the fact of living in and being from a borderland is often explicitly articulated as having a unique sense of place and identity that is different from the rest of the country. Such differences in place experience are often associated with the history of war and conflict in the border region, which often play a crucial role in the heritage narratives and tangible heritage of the border regions. Many sites visited during the borderwalks were popular tourist sites and historical monuments that commemorate the war experiences and sacrifices of the ancestors. The narratives told in and about these sites also show that institutionalized and people narratives of border landscapes as heritage are entangled with each other in many ways. Some citizens also underlined that being from a borderland relates to an experience of being more cross-cultural than the mainstream. Older generations often offered valuable insights into the region's history and pointed out the tangible aspects of living with the border as it existed in their youth, for example the availability of different goods and products. Their stories reflect a deep connection to the landscape, recounting traditions like the preservation of the old border markers and sharing folklore tied to specific locations and environments.

The results show that borderland citizens do not often conceptualize border landscape as a cosmopolitan transnational, but many have more locally and nationally specific understanding and even exclusive perceptions of what and who belongs to the landscape. This is illustrated by the finding that the perceptions and narratives of border landscapes as heritage are not very often related explicitly to the EU or to the overall European context. For example, the seniors often include the time-perspective in their stories and how borders were more strictly controlled in the past, but a few attributed to the EU and European integration. Even when open borders are spoken about by the border citizens, this is not related to the establishment of the EU and Schengen areas of free movement. Rather, open borders seem to be

taken for granted and interpreted in a normative sense by most of the participants as being “how things ought to be” and not something constructed in European integration processes. In most cases the EU is met with indifference rather than with skepticism.

When evaluating the results and their significance, it is crucial to consider the strengths and pitfalls of the methods used to gather the material. Doing mobile borderwalks with citizens and being present in-situ when talking about sites in the border landscapes made the narratives more directed with concrete places and surroundings than would be the case with typical interview methods. The results also illustrate some differences between the younger and older generations. Youth groups were not as fluent storytellers as the senior groups, yet they took active role in the selection of the sites for the borderwalk and were equally engaged in the StoryMap poster creation in the Finnish-Swedish borderland.

Although no insurmountable obstacles were encountered during the research process, there were several challenges which researchers needed to solve and deal with during the process. Recruiting participants from specific target groups turned out to be the most challenging issue. To mitigate the challenge and to secure the representation of the target groups, researchers used their personal contacts, either to have contact with the “gatekeepers” or directly to participants. Some researchers felt that it was easier to do the go-along borderwalks with the senior groups, who had interests in local questions and were eager to share their stories. Most of the stories told by young people were short and focused on the present, whereas the older people told longer stories, connecting public heritage narratives with personal and family lives with the border and specific sites. There were also some physical limitations with a few senior participants in terms of mobility. The groups adjusted the route according to these limitations and for example, some of the selected sites were discussed from further away. This ad-hoc mitigation strategy worked well. Other challenges included the limited free time of the participants. Additionally, the noise on the city streets affected the quality of few recordings. Weather conditions caused some minor challenges and delays. Also, language differences between researchers and participants caused some challenges at different border regions. This illustrates the general difficulties and barriers related to cross-border communication and doing research in borderlands. In general, it was common that researchers and participants spoke different languages depending on which language’s oral skills were stronger.

From the perspective of analysing and making conclusions about border landscapes as heritage it is important to acknowledge that some border narratives are possible or problematic for certain groups of people (see also Prokkola 2008). Place-based narratives are often entangled with identity politics; thus, they include but also exclude. Even if the results inform us about the perceptions of border landscapes as heritage, however, they also lack and even silence some perspectives. Many border heritage narratives celebrate a rich shared history and vibrant cross-border culture, but these narratives do not always acknowledge the diversity of voices that shape the border landscape today. The narratives often fail to fully include some immigrant groups and expats, especially those from outside the European Union. These “lost voices” are rarely acknowledged and sometimes they are also feared, as some stories from the Bulgarian-Greek borderlands illustrate. In this borderland, the narratives of shared heritage sometimes establish new borders between local borderlanders and refugees and other marginalized groups. The lack of inclusivity in some heritage narratives creates divisions, despite efforts to celebrate the region’s diverse cultural influences. Still, the results suggest that shared events like local festivals or environmental initiatives provide a platform for bridging these gaps.

The objective of the B-SHAPES work package *Border landscapes as heritage* was to gain understanding about how borders shape youth and senior borderlanders perspectives and narratives of landscape as heritage. Future research on border landscapes could focus more on newcomers’ perspectives, thus widening the citizen science perspective to European non-citizens. Another perspective that could be

emphasized more in multidisciplinary border and heritage research as well as border region heritage-making concerns the recognition of the environmental questions and the multispecies lives of the borderlands. The research shows that some important environmental questions are completely absent from the narratives of border landscape as heritage. For example, the narratives of the Danish-German border landscapes include only a single story about the boar fence, which has huge impact on the wildlife in the border region. When the boar fence was mentioned, it is its symbolic significance and identity politics which is narrated as important, that is how it signals 'the wrong direction to take politically', considering the history of the border region. The physical significance of the fence, which is taken up as a measure influencing the movement of human beings and wildlife, cutting up a natural landscape, was absent from the discussions of the border landscape. Even when walking on the West coast border where the fence is very visible, the artificiality of its placement does not appear to be of importance to the citizens. Finally, the results need to be evaluated from the perspective of narrative approach and citizen science that guided our research process and design. The borderland citizens were important actors in the research, carrying and sharing local and embodied knowledge of borders with researchers. Their narratives concern the border landscape as heritage have allowed us to identify new research problems and aspects of borders to be analysed from the material and in future research, for example the role of geopolitics was taken up by borderlanders as a new perspective for understanding the meaning of border landscapes, its past, present and future. Such narratives of border landscapes can be highly sensitive and contradictory and their incorporation in the institutionalized heritage-making process needs to be carefully considered and inclusively implemented, facilitating cross-border dialogue and collaboration between different generations at local, national and European scales.

References

- dell'Agnese, E., & Amilhat Szary, A. L. (2015). Borderscapes: From Border Landscapes to Border Aesthetics. *Geopolitics*, 20(1), 4–13.
- Andersen, D.J., Prokkola, E-K. & D. Karakashev (2025). When Landscapes Borders. In *Through the Prism of Borders* (ed. by K. Anguelova, A. Burtscher, M. Oberhofer), Kunstverein Publishing Milano.
- Andersen, D. J., & Prokkola, E. K. (2021). Heritage as bordering: Heritage making, ontological struggles and the politics of memory in the Croatian and Finnish borderlands. *Journal of Borderlands Studies*, 36(3), 405-424.
- Benovska-Sabkova, M. (2006). Friendship groups in leisure time in Bulgaria: examples from the socialist and postsocialist period, https://pure.mpg.de/rest/items/item_922941/component/file_3479313/content
- Benovska-Sabkova, M., & Nedin, I. (2016). Border territories, border people: The bulgarian town of Zlatograd as a border and a bridge. *Antropologija/Anthropology*, 3, 25-54.
- Biggs, S. D. (1989). Resource-poor farmer participation in research: A synthesis of experiences from nine national agricultural research systems, <https://cgspace.cgiar.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/b2eadfa8-323f-4901-975e-c6dcf9f94448/content>
- Council of Europe Landscape Convention (ETS No. 176), opened for signature at Florence on 20 October 2000.
- Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: Choosing Among Five Approaches*, 3rd edited. Sage Publications.
- Czarniawska, B. (2010). The uses of narratology in social and policy studies. *Critical policy studies*, 4(1), 58-76.
- Daugbjerg, M. (2014). *Borders of belonging: Experiencing history, war and nation at a Danish heritage site* (Vol. 5). Berghahn Books.
- Dragostinova, T. (2016). Continuity vs. radical break: national homogenization campaigns in the Greek-Bulgarian borderlands before and after the Balkan Wars. *Journal of Genocide Research*, 18(4), 405–426.
- Dzikowska, A., Zaręba, A., Krzemińska, A., & Pawłowski, K. (2023). The Cultural Landscape of Rural Cemeteries on the Polish–Czech Borderlands: Multi-Faceted Visual Analysis as an Element of Tourism Potential Assessment. *Sustainability*, 15(18), 13730.
- Dolińska, K., Niedźwiecka-Iwańczak, N., & Opiłowska, E. (2021). Narrating Divided Cities. *Polish Sociological Review*, (216), 517-532.
- Duedahl, E. (2020). *To walk the talk of go-along methods: navigating the unknown terrains of being-along*. Taylor and Francis Online.
- Duncan, J. (1995). Landscape geography, 1993-94. *Progress in human geography*, 19(3), 414-422.
- Duncan, J., & Duncan, N. (1988). (Re) reading the landscape. *Environment and Planning D: Society and space*, 6(2), 117-126.
- Dzikowska, A., Zaręba, A., Krzemińska, A., & Pawłowski, K. (2023). The Cultural Landscape of Rural Cemeteries on the Polish–Czech Borderlands: Multi-Faceted Visual Analysis as an Element of Tourism Potential Assessment. *Sustainability*, 15(18), 13730.

- Eisenhauer, B.W., R.S. Krannich & D.J. Blahna (2000). Attachments to special places on public lands: an analysis of activities, reason for attachments, and community connections. *Society and Natural Resources*, 13 (5) (2000), pp. 421-441.
- Elenius, L. (2008). *Transnational history and language barriers*. Luleå tekniska universitet.
- Entrikin, J. N. (1991). *The betweenness of place* (pp. 6-26). Macmillan Education UK.
- Esin, C., Fathi, M., & Squire, C. (2014). Narrative analysis: The constructionist approach. *The SAGE handbook of qualitative data analysis*, 203-216.
- Eskilsson, L., & Högdahl, E. (2009). Cultural Heritage across Borders? – Framing and Challenging the Snapphane Story in Southern Sweden. *Scandinavian Journal of Hospitality and Tourism*, 9(1), 65–80.
- Esohe E. Egiebor & E. Foster (2019). Students' Perceptions of Their Engagement Using GIS-Story Maps, *Journal of Geography*, 118:2, 51-65.
- Fairclough, N. (1992). Discourse and text: Linguistic and intertextual analysis within discourse analysis. *Discourse & society*, 3(2), 193-217.
- Fairclough, N. (2003). *Analysing discourse* (Vol. 270). London: Routledge.
- Frandsen, S. B. (2021). Schleswig: From a land-in-between to a national borderland. In *Borderlands Resilience* (pp. 121-136). Routledge.
- Gazzola, P., Belcáková, I., & Pauditšová, E. (2019). Landscape within the framework of environmental assessment at project and planning levels. *Landscape Impact Assessment in Planning Processes; De Gruyter Open: Warsaw, Poland*, 28-76.
- Germundsson, T. (2008). *The south of the north: Images of an (un) Swedish landscape* (pp. 157-191). University of Minnesota Press.
- Germundsson, T. (2013). Regional cultural heritage versus national heritage in Scania's disputed national landscape. In *The Nature of Cultural Heritage, and the Culture of Natural Heritage* (pp. 19-35). Routledge.
- Golumbic, Y. N., Orr, D., Baram-Tsabari, A., & Fishbain, B. (2017). Between Vision and Reality: A Study of Scientists' Views on Citizen Science. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 2(1), 6.
- Gubrium, J. F., & Holstein, J. A. (2009). *Analyzing narrative reality*. Sage.
- Haklay M (2013) Citizen science and volunteered geographic information – overview and typology of participation. In: Sui DZ, Elwood S, Goodchild MF (eds) *Crowdsourcing geographic knowledge*. Springer, Berlin, pp 105–122 (2) (PDF) Citizen Science for Observing and Understanding the Earth. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/322659357_Citizen_Science_for_Observing_and_Understanding_the_Earth [accessed Sep 26 2023].
- Harvey, D. C., & Waterton, E. (2015). Editorial: Landscapes of Heritage and Heritage Landscapes. *Landscape Research*, 40(8), 905–910.
- Häyrynen, M. (2000). The kaleidoscopic view: The Finnish national landscape imagery. *National Identities*, 2(1), 5-19.
- Hederyd, O. (1992). *Haparanda efter 1809–Tornedalens historia III*. Haparanda, Birkkarlen.
- Häyrynen, M. (2000). The kaleidoscopic view: The Finnish national landscape imagery. *National Identities* 2(1), 5-19.

- Häyrynen, M. (2004). A periphery lost: the representation of Karelia in Finnish national landscape imagery. *Fennia-International Journal of Geography*, 182(1), 23-32.
- Ingold, T. (2010). Footprints through the weather-world: walking, breathing, knowing. *The Journal of the Royal Anthropological Institute*, Vol 16.
- Jakola, F. (2016). Borders, planning and policy transfer: historical transformation of development discourses in the Finnish Torne Valley. *European Planning Studies*, 24(10), 1806-1824.
- Jones, P., Bunce, G., Evans, J., Gibbs, H., & Hein, J. R. (2008). Exploring space and place with walking interviews. *Journal of research practice*, 4(2), D2.
- Jones P, Bunce G, Evans J, et al. (2008) Research design: exploring space and place with walking interviews. *Journal of Research Practice* 4(2): 1–9.
- Kaisto, V. (2024). *The Finnish-Russian borderland as a lived space: Perceptions, experiences, and identities in everyday life* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Eastern Finland).
- Knippenberg, H. (2004). The Maas-Rhine Euroregion: A Laboratory for European Integration?. *Geopolitics*, 9(3), 608-626.
- Klatt, M. (2024). The Danish-German-Frisian Region - A Best Practice Example? In: Wassenberg, Birte (ed.): *Frontières En Mouvement (Frontem): Which Models of Cross-Border Cooperation for the EU? A Comparative Analysis from a Euro-Atlantic Perspective*, 375–407. Border Studies - Borders and European Integration 6. Bruxelles: Peter Lang Verlag.
- Kloppenburger, K. (2022). Peer Production in Citizen Science: A Community-Centered Approach on the Example of Personal Science. Doctoral dissertation, Université Paris Cité; The Alan Turing Institute).
- Kolosov, V. (2020). Phantom borders: The role in territorial identity and the impact on society. *Belgeo. Revue belge de géographie*, (2).
- Konkoly-Gyuró, É. (2018). Conceptualisation and perception of the landscape and its changes in a transboundary area. A case study of the Southern German-French borderland. *Land Use Policy*, 79, 556-574.
- Laurén, K. (2012). Fear in border narratives: Perspectives of the Finnish-Russian border. *Folklore: Electronic Journal of Folklore*, (52), 39-62.
- Li, Y., Jia, N., Yu, X., Manning, N., Lan, X., & Liu, J. (2023). Transboundary flows in the metacoupled Anthropocene: typology, methods, and governance for global sustainability. *Ecology and Society*, 28(3).
- Lyon, L., & Miller, P. (2001). The people's heritage: Democratising our memory institutions. *New review of information networking*, 7(1), 185-200.
- McCall, C. (2014). The Building and Erosion of the “Post-Conflict” Irish Borderscape 1. In *European Border Regions in Comparison* (pp. 133-146). Routledge.
- Neuburger, M. (2000). Pomak borderlands: Muslims on the edge of nations. *Nationalities Papers*, 28(1), 181-198.
- Newman, D., & Paasi, A. (1998). Fences and neighbours in the postmodern world: boundary narratives in political geography. *Progress in human geography*, 22(2), 186-207.
- Nordberg, H. & T. Kallio-Seppänen (2010). Raja 200 - Gränsen 2000: *Tornionlaakson vuosikirja/ Tornedalens årsbok 2008-2010*.
- O'Neill, M. & B. Roberts (2020). *Walking Methods: Research on the Move*. London: Routledge.

- Macpherson, H. (2016). Walking methods in landscape research: Moving bodies, spaces of disclosure and rapport. *Landscape Research*, 41(4), 425-432.
- Moen, T. (2006). Reflections on the Narrative Research Approach. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 5(4), 56-69.
- Ochoa Espejo, P. (2020). *On borders: territories, legitimacy and the rights of place*. Oxford University Press.
- Paasi, A. (2003). Region and place: regional identity in question. *Progress in human geography*, 27(4), 475-485.
- Poria, Y., Butler, R., & Airey, D. (2003). The core of heritage tourism. *Annals of tourism research*, 30(1), 238-254.
- Poria, Y., Biran, A., & Reichel, A. (2006). Tourist perceptions: Personal vs. non-personal. *Journal of Heritage Tourism*, 1(2), 121-132.
- Popov, A. and Deák, D. (2015), Making sense of the 'difficult' past: transmission of political heritage and memory-work among young people across Europe. *The Sociological Review*, 63: 36-52.
- Prokkola, E. K., & Lois, M. (2016). Scalar politics of border heritage: an examination of the EU's northern and southern border areas. *Scandinavian Journal of Hospitality and Tourism*, 16(sup1), 14-35.
- Raivo, P. J. (2002). The peculiar touch of the East: Reading the post-war landscapes of the Finnish Orthodox Church. *Social & Cultural Geography*, 3(1), 11-24.
- Raivo, P. J. (2004). Karelia lost or won – materialization of a landscape of contested and commemorated memory. *Fennia-International Journal of Geography*, 182(1), 61-72.
- Pekola, S. (2021). Länsirajan rakentaminen ja ylittäminen vuodesta 1809. *Ennen ja nyt: Historian tietosanomat*, 21(6), 3-26.
- Prokkola, E. K. (2008). Border narratives at work: Theatrical smuggling and the politics of commemoration. *Geopolitics*, 13(4), 657-675.
- Prokkola, E-K. (2008). *Making bridges, removing barriers: Cross-border cooperation, regionalization and identity at the Finnish-Swedish border*. Nordia Geographical Publications (Academic dissertation, University of Oulu).
- Prokkola, E. K. (2010). Borders in tourism: the transformation of the Swedish–Finnish border landscape. *Current Issues in tourism*, 13(3), 223-238.
- Prokkola, E. K. (2014). Using narrativity as methodological tool. *ACME: An International Journal for Critical Geographies*, 13(3), 442-449.
- Prokkola, E. K., Andersen, D. J., Jakola, F., Nilson, T., & Svensson, S. M. H. (2024). Multilayered Borders as a Method for Studying Tourism Destinations: A Case of Northern European Border Regions. *Journal of Borderlands Studies*, 1-21.
- Ridanpää, J. (2011). Pajala as a literary place: in the readings and footsteps of Mikael Niemi. *Journal of Tourism and Cultural Change*, 9(2), 103-117.
- Ruotsala, H. (2021). Living on the both sides of an invisible border—the impacts of COVID-19 in the Tornio River Valley. *Hungarian studies yearbook*, 3(1), 147-162.
- Shirk, J. L., Ballard, H. L., Wilderman, C. C., Phillips, T., Wiggins, A., Jordan, R., McCallie, E., Minarchek, M., Lewenstein, B. V., Krasny, M. E., & Bonney, R. (2012). Public Participation in Scientific Research: A Framework for Deliberate Design. *Ecology and Society*, 17(2).

- Simm, D., D. Freeman & A. Marvell (2024) Landscape detectives: developing a palimpsest approach to fieldwork, *Geography*, 109:2, 89-98, DOI: 10.1080/00167487.2024.2351773
- Sohn, C. (2014). Modelling cross-border integration: The role of borders as a resource. *Geopolitics*, 19(3), 587-608.
- Sohn, C. (2023). The impact of rebordering on cross-border cooperation actors' discourses in the Öresund region. A semantic network approach. *Geografiska Annaler: Series B, Human Geography*, 1-23.
- Springgay, S. & Truman, S. (2018). *Walking Methodologies in a More-than-Human World: Walking Lab*. New York: Routledge.
- Stephenson, J. (2008). The cultural values model: an integrated approach to values in landscapes. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 84 (2008), 127-139.
- Svensson, S., & Nilson, T. (2023). European Memory Politics in Scandinavia—the Case of a Swedish-Danish Border Region. *JEIH Journal of European Integration History*, 29(1), 111-134.
- Squire, C. (2013). From Experience-Centred to Socioculturally-Oriented Approaches to Narrative. in: Andrews, M., Squire, C. & Tamboukou, M. (ed.) *Doing Narrative Research*. London SAGE.
- Taylor, S., & Littleton, K. (2006). Biographies in talk: A narrative-discursive research approach. *Qualitative sociology review*, 2(1), 22-38.
- Timothy, D. J., & Więckowski, M. (2022). Borders, heritage, and memory. In *Routledge handbook of borders and tourism* (pp. 219-240). Routledge.
- Tolia-Kelly, D. P. (2008). Motion/emotion: Picturing translocal landscapes in the nurturing ecologies research project. *Mobilities*, 3(1), 117-140.
- Tolia-Kelly, D. P. (2011). Narrating the postcolonial landscape: archaeologies of race at Hadrian's Wall. *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*, 36(1), 71-88.
- Vojteková, J., Žoncová, M., Tirpáková, A., & Vojtek, M. (2021). Evaluation of story maps by future geography teachers. *Journal of Geography in Higher Education*, 46(3), 360–382.
- Więckowski, M. (2022). A cautionary tale for the generations. The reconstruction of the former border-check-points in Poland. *Journal of Heritage Tourism*, 17(6), 702–717.
- Vollmer, M., Guldberg, M., Maluck, M., van Marrewijk, D., and Schlicksbier, G., 2001. Lancewad. Landscape and Cultural Heritage in the Wadden Sea region. Project Report. Wadden Sea Ecosystem No. 12, Common Wadden Sea Secretariat, Wilhelmshaven
- Wylie, J. (2009). Landscape, absence and the geographies of love. *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*, 34(3), 275-289.
- Wylie, J. (2013). Landscape and phenomenology. In *The Routledge companion to landscape studies* (pp. 72-83). Routledge.
- Wyrda, H. (2018). Generations of Memory: Elements of a Conceptual Framework. *Comparative Studies in Society and History*, 60(1), 5–34.